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**OFF-GRID TARGET DETECTION IN WSN USING
SBL**

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OFF-GRID TARGET DETECTION IN WSN's USING SBL

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ABSTRACT

Energy consumption is a significant challenge in Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs). Compressed Sensing (CS) effectively reduces energy consumption but faces limitations, such as detecting a limited number of targets and assuming targets are on-grid. This thesis proposed using Sparse Bayesian Learning (SBL) for target detection in WSNs. SBL provided a model for off-grid target detection and also enhanced target detection accuracy and achieved nearly double the target detection compared to other methods like Basis Pursuit (BP). The SBL method successfully detected up to 30 targets with very high detection performance. In comparison, the BP method detected only 15 targets under the same environmental conditions.

Two variables are considered in off-grid scenarios: displacement along the x-axis and y-axis. The Off-grid detection results demonstrate that the proposed approach, which incorporates dependent assumptions, can effectively localize targets within the framework of theoretical assumptions. This is in contrast to an approach based on independent assumptions, which may not achieve the same level of accuracy.

Further, this thesis proposed an adaptive Sparse Bayesian Learning (A-SBL) approach to increasing the sensors' lifetime in wireless sensor networks (WSNs). By combining the Bayesian model with adaptive compressive sensing (A-CS), the methodology minimizes the number of sensors required for successful target detection. Initially, a few sensors are selected randomly, and the Cluster Head (CH) then calls sensors that provide maximal information, achieving the greatest error reduction. This approach enhances resource use and energy efficiency, improving overall network performance. Results confirm that this method significantly reduces energy consumption

compared to other approaches, especially with fewer targets, contributing to advancements in WSN technology. Where The results show that the energy consumption of the A-SBL approach was 53% of the energy consumption by the traditional method when detecting 5 targets. As the number of targets increased to 15 and 30, the energy consumption dropped to 30% and 17%, respectively, compared to the energy consumed by the traditional method. Additionally, when the initial sensors were increased to 15 instead of 5, the proposed method's energy consumption was 48%, 28%, and 17% for 5, 15, and 30 targets, respectively.

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”To Al Imam Mahdi(AG): When will you see us, and when will we see you?”

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the thesis is my original work except for the quotations and citations which have been duly acknowledged.

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Mustafa Abdulrahman Jabbar

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Description
<i>AoA</i>	Angel of Arrival
<i>A-SBL</i>	Adaptive Sparse Bayesian Learning
<i>APIT</i>	Approximate Point In-Triangulation
<i>APS</i>	Ad-hoc Positioning System
<i>BS</i>	Base Station
<i>BP</i>	Basis Pursuit
<i>BPDN</i>	Basis Pursuit De-Noising
<i>CS</i>	Compressed Sensing
<i>CH</i>	Central Hub or Cluster Head
<i>DV – HOP</i>	Distance Vector-Hop
<i>DoA</i>	Direction of Arrival
<i>DoF</i>	Degrees of Freedom
<i>DBS</i>	Distributed Balanced Sensing
<i>EECS</i>	Energy Efficient Clustering Scheme
<i>GPS</i>	Global Positioning System
<i>HEED</i>	Hybrid Energy-Efficient Distributed
<i>IA</i>	Iterative Activation
<i>IA – LSCS</i>	Iterative Activation Least Squares Compressive Sampling
<i>LASSO</i>	Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator
<i>LEACH</i>	Low Energy Adaptive Clustering Hierarchy
<i>LEACH – SWND</i>	LEACH-Sliding Window and Dynamic Number of Nodes
<i>LEACH – C</i>	LEACH-Centralized
<i>MSE</i>	Mean Square Error
<i>MTLCS</i>	Multiple Target Localization Compressive Sensing
<i>MIMO</i>	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
<i>MMV</i>	Multiple Measurement Vector
<i>NMDS – MLE</i>	Non-metric Multi-Dimensional Scaling with Maximum Likelihood Estimation
<i>NSP</i>	Nullspace Property
<i>OMP</i>	Orthogonal Matching Pursuit
<i>OGSBI</i>	Off-Grid Sparse Bayesian Inference
<i>Q – LEACH</i>	Quadrant-LEACH
<i>RIP</i>	Restricted Isometry Property
<i>ROC</i>	Receiver Operating Characteristic
<i>ROMP</i>	Regularised Orthogonal Matching Pursuit

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Description
<i>RF</i>	Radio Frequency
<i>RSP</i>	Range Space Property
<i>RSS</i>	Received Signal Strength
<i>SMV</i>	Single Measurement Vector
<i>SBL</i>	Sparse Bayesian Learning
<i>SOMP – TLS</i>	Simultaneous Orthogonal Matching Pursuit Total Least Squares
<i>SOMP – LS</i>	Simultaneous Orthogonal Matching Pursuit Least Squares
<i>SOCP</i>	Second-Order Cone Programs
<i>TDoA</i>	Time difference of arrival
<i>ToA</i>	Time of Arrival
<i>VD – TMTL</i>	Voronoi Diagram Two-phase Multiple Target Localization
<i>VHF</i>	Very High Frequency
<i>VORBA</i>	VHF Omnidirectional Range-Base
<i>VBEM</i>	Variational Bayesian Expectation-Maximization
<i>WSNs</i>	Wireless Sensor Networks

LIST OF SYMBOLS

Symbol	Definition
Δ	the tolerable quantization error.
Δx	The target displacement from the grid point towards the x-axis vector.
Δy	The target displacement from the grid point towards the y-axis vector.
Φ	The random measurement matrix
$\Phi_{\Delta x, \Delta y}$	Measurements matrix with off-grid errors along both x and y axes
$\Phi_{\Delta x}$	Measurements matrix with off-grid errors along x-axis only.
$\Phi_{\Delta y}$	Measurements matrix with off-grid errors along y-axis only
w	Sparse weight vector
y	The measurement vector
α	Hyper-parameters vector
σ^2	Hyper-parameters of variance noise.
μ_w	Mean for sparse weight vector w .
Σ_w	Covariance matrix for w .
Λ	Diagonal matrix for (α) .
B	The derivative of the measurement matrix with respect to x.
C	The derivative of the measurement matrix with respect to y.
e	Gaussian White noise vector .
I	The Identity matrix.
K	The Coefficient matrix.
β	Off-grid error vector .
D_{max}	The maximum distances for which the target can be detected by the sensor.
E_{TX}^i	The total energy consumed by the i^{th} sensor nodes to send data over a communication channel to the CH.
S	The distance between any two adjacent grid points.
$D_{n,g}$	The distance between n^{th} sensor to g^{th} grid points.
$d_{i,CH}$	The Euclidean distance between the i^{th} sensor node and the CH.

LIST OF SYMBOLS

Symbol	Definition
N	The number of the sensor nodes in WSN.
G	The number of the grid points in WSN.
y	The Number of targets.
B	The Number of bits.
f	Underlying signal
ξ	The Diagonal of covariance matrix of f .
a	Shape parameter for α .
b	Rate parameter for α .
c	Shape parameter for σ^2 .
d	Rate parameter for σ^2 .
t	The vector collected the target measurement distances.
x	An input signal .
q	The recovered target vector.
\hat{x}	Target's two-dimensional location estimated
Γ	Gamma distribution
\mathcal{U}	Uniform distribution
\mathcal{N}	Normal distribution
\Re	Determination of real values
\circ	Matrix dot multiplication

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1 Introduction

Substantial Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) are the most popular and commonly utilized wireless communication technology. They have been made feasible by recent significant advancements in computer networking, microelectronics, and wireless communications [1, 2].

The WSNs are made up of numerous tiny inexpensive specialized purpose sensor nodes, and a BS, or Cluster Head (CH). Depending on the application's needs, the sensor node may be mobile or static [3]. In an area of interest, the sensor nodes are arranged intentionally or randomly [4]. Sensor nodes may be dropped from the aircraft or by other means, leading to a random placement, when the environment of interest is inaccessible or situated in a hostile region [5].

The WSNs find utility in various applications, such as remote environmental monitoring and target tracking, facilitated by developing increasingly sophisticated, smaller, and more cost-effective sensors. These sensors, equipped with wireless interfaces, establish connectivity within the network. The design of a WSN is heavily influenced by its intended use, considering factors like application requirements, environmental conditions, hardware constraints, and design objectives. Unlike conventional networks,

WSNs are purpose-built for specific applications, ranging from surveillance systems to military target tracking, industrial machine monitoring, and environmental monitoring. Each application comes with unique needs and characteristics [6–8]. Moreover, WSNs are useful for environmental applications such as emergency alerting, air and water monitoring[9] and monitoring patient physiological data is one possible use case for WSN [10]. Sensitive applications in WSNs, like structural health monitoring and in-situ environmental monitoring, necessitate prolonged sensor functionality, where challenges arise in scenarios where battery replacement or recharging is difficult or impossible [6, 11].

Target detection in home security systems involves detecting intruders, combatants, or animals[12] by deploying sensor nodes throughout a designated area. These sensors collect data such as acoustic, motion, or thermal signals, which are then processed to filter out noise and identify potential targets. Once a target is detected, an alert is generated to notify the system or user. Target tracking builds upon this by continuously monitoring the identified target’s movement through real-time data collection and fusion from multiple sensors. This allows the system to predict the target’s trajectory, update its position in real-time, and ensure secure data transmission for accurate tracking and timely responses. Target detection is sometimes thought of as the initial stage in finding and tracking a mobile target.

1.2 Localization Techniques

One crucial application of the WSNs lies in target localization [13]. In-network localization systems are broadly categorized into two types: Range-free and range-based.

Despite compromising accuracy and scalability, range-free methods employ topological data to infer the nodal locations [14]. To optimize the node placements, the Approximate Point In-Triangulation (APIT) range-free localization technique is utilized, dividing the network into triangular sections [15]. Distance Vector-Hop (DV-HOP), a hop count-based technique, employs hop-distance information and anchor flooding for localization [16]. Nodes modify their positions in response to hop count, average distance per hop, and anchor locations, with neighbor-tracking beacons informed of anchor positions. Additionally, a centroid-based technique enables nodes to determine their positions in the centroid of overlapping beacon anchor transmission coverage zones [13]. On the other hand, range-based approaches, garnering more attention, compute range distance from anchors using metrics such as Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) [17], Angle of Arrival (AOA) [18], Time of Arrival (TOA), and Time Difference of Arrival (TDOA) [19]. In [18], an AOA-based Ad Hoc Positioning System (APS) is proposed for node location determination. The VHF Omnidirectional Ranging-base station (VORBA) utilizes AoA data and signal strength for localization but necessitates specialized equipment, including expensive rotating directional antennas [20].

Despite their lower accuracy, the RSSI-based measurements from transceivers are more widely available and cost-effective. Extensive research has focused on developing reliable RSS-based localization algorithms employing probabilistic models and calibration enhancements [13]. It is recommended to improve the RSSI-based localization techniques, particularly in terms of calibration, to enhance robustness and accuracy [21]. The indoor localization system RADAR monitors RSS during calibration at different points in a building, storing the results in a database. By comparing RSS readings with the data saved in this database, the system ascertains a new node's ori-

entation and location [17]. The Non-Metric Multidimensional Scaling with Maximum Likelihood Estimation (NMDS-MLE) utilizes a maximum likelihood estimate to calculate distances between neighbouring nodes based on their RSS values. Probabilistic methods, such as those proposed in [22], have been employed to enhance localization precision.

To demonstrate the feasibility of the RSSI-based probabilistic localization in an outdoor testbed, probabilistic methods for network localization, considering erroneous range measurements were devised in [23]. A distributed, probabilistic method for outdoor WSN localization was presented in [21]. The Probabilistic region-based localization methods, including offline grids, grid segments, and dynamic meshes, were proposed in [24]. Furthermore, [25] introduced a Bayesian interference-based solution for network localization using the IEEE 802.11 protocols.

Furthermore, the employing of the CS in the WSNs shows potential for lowering energy consumption. According to the CS theory, sparse signals within the WSNs can be accurately reconstructed using a minimal number of random linear measurements. Unlike traditional sensing systems, which sample data at a predetermined pace, the CS uses the sparsity of perceived signals to provide an alternate method. Many applications exhibit sparse structural properties in data, allowing important information to be obtained with fewer relevant observations. As a result, the CS provides an energy efficiency approach that extends network lifespan in WSNs[26–28].

The SBL is a probabilistic method that estimates the covariance and mean of sparse signals and computes their posterior distribution [29]. The SBL uses the Bayesian rule to determine the posterior probability for sparse signals and the collection of the

Hyper-parameters in the context of the Single Measurement Vector (SMV) model for sparse signal recovery[30–32]. In Bayesian modelling, Hyper-parameters are important for improving the model’s performance and determining the optimal way to distribute sparse signals. They also impact the level of normalization and the accuracy and control of Bayesian learning.

The Basis Pursuit (BP) approach [33] and its variants employ fixed-point updates to identify sparsity. One of the issues and drawbacks of those approaches is that the targets must be placed at a specific grid point (i.e. on-grid situation) on the sensing region [34]. Anyhow, this approach is impacted by an issue that causes a drop in performance when the target is not in an on-grid situation called the off-grid problem, where the targets can be posited anywhere within the sensing area (i.e. off-grid situation). In the SBL, such constraint has been addressed in many works[35, 36]

One method to solve the off-grid problem as in [37] through using the first-order Taylor expansion around a known dictionary (i.e., a set of signals or components used to represent the data) to approximate the unknown specified dictionary, then after that, by formulated the counting and localization issue as a sparse recovery issue to recover two sparse vectors with identical supports. Finally, the variational Bayesian expectation-maximization algorithm is used to solve the problem. A localization system is introduced in [38] to tackle the off-grid problem by employing quantized measurements that require only a few bits. This approach is designed to address quantization errors while effectively estimating the locations of targets.

Table 1.1: Comparison Between Range-free and Range-based Localization Techniques in WSNs

Aspect	Range-free	Range-based
Techniques Used	Topological data inference	RSSI, AOA, TOA, TDOA
Example Techniques	APIT, DV-HOP and Centroid-based	AOA-based APS, VORBA and RADAR
Performance	- Lower accuracy - Relies on network topology	- Higher accuracy - Depends on direct measurements
Drawbacks	- Low accuracy - Performance issues in off-grid scenarios	- Requires specialized equipment - Higher cost - Accuracy depends on measurement quality
Cost	- Low - Inexpensive sensors	- High - Expensive sensors and additional equipment
Applications	- Localization in less accurate environments - General monitoring	- Accurate localization - Applications requiring high precision

1.3 Problem Statement

In the context of WSNs, several key challenges need to be addressed to improve their efficiency and effectiveness. These challenges include:

1. Simultaneous detection of multiple targets in WSNs.
2. Off-grid target detection challenges, including energy efficiency, scalability, coverage, and robust data processing under environmental constraints.
3. Extending the Lifetime of Network Sensors.

1.4 Literature Review

Numerous researchers have been interested in multi-target detection because of its widespread use in various applications. Additionally, the importance of target detection is in off-grid situations and has also brought attention to the significance of lowering detection energy consumption. This section includes the literature on multi-target detection, Off grid-target detection and decreasing energy consumption techniques via WSNs.

1.4.1 Multi-Target Detection

For the WSNs' applications, many localization methods have been presented in the literature. These include the linear estimation algorithm [39, 40] and the CS-based approaches [33, 41–45]. Additionally, methods for off-grid target detection [35–38, 46, 47] and techniques for reducing energy consumption [33, 48–53] in WSNs have also been explored.

1.4.1.1 Linear Estimation Algorithm

Kang et al. [39] in (2021) proposed a computationally efficient hybrid algorithm for multi-target localization. This algorithm estimates potential target locations by combining data from selected anchor nodes and filters out erroneous targets using the Mean Square Error (MSE) criterion. It organizes measurement sets at each sensor node based on the most promising target candidates, subsequently applying a single-target localization method to these clustered measurement sets to enhance localization accuracy. Simulation results demonstrated the algorithm's robustness, particularly in noisy environments. The primary contribution of this study is the development of an

effective multi-target localization technique utilizing AOA and RSSI data, even when these measurements are not directly associated with the targets.

Luomala and Hakala [40] in 2022: employed conventional methods for multi-target detection by Using a multilateration approach based on TOA measurements for target identification. This method allows for the exact prediction of target positions regardless of target number or distribution since sensors communicate information about each target separately. However, the large number of transmission operations needed for identifying many targets has a significant influence on the WSNs' lifetime.

1.4.1.2 Compressed Sensing (CS) Method

Feng et al. [41] in (2009) proposed a method for target localization within an isotropic region of unknown locations using RSSI measurements. The technique involves discretizing the region into N grid points and utilizing M sensors to gather RSSI data. To achieve accurate localization with minimal RSSI observations, the method applies data processing techniques that align with CS theory. Post-processing corrects for spatial discretization due to grid-based assumptions, while pre-processing introduces necessary incoherence for CS. Simulation results indicate that this CS approach outperforms other RSSI-based localization methods, such as the kernel method, K Nearest Neighbors, and histogram approaches.

Liu et al. [42] in (2014) developed a range-free algorithm using binary sensors and MTLCS . The algorithm divides the sensor network's monitoring area into several distinct regions, each with SS sensor nodes deployed at known locations. It assumes one node per grid and T targets distributed across multiple grids, with one target per grid. The method presumes that the center of each grid represents the actual target

location. Sensors transmit sensing matrices and measurement vectors to the CH, resulting in increased energy consumption. Simulation results indicate that MTLCS provides improved localization accuracy without requiring actual distance measurements. However, localization error increases with the number of targets, although the accuracy improves with the addition of more sensor nodes.

Xin et al. [43]in (2015) explores CS-based method for identifying multiple targets. The study addresses two main challenges. First, it employs an iterative activation algorithm (IA) to prioritize sensors with higher values, rather than activating all sensors equally. This selective activation technique allows for continuous monitoring of all targets while conserving bandwidth and energy. Targets emit signals that are detected by activated sensors, which then transmit the RSSI values to a CH. A compressive sampling method is subsequently applied to estimate the number and locations of the targets. Second, a sequential recovery approach, known as IA-LSCS, is proposed to enhance localization accuracy using all available data. Extensive simulations demonstrate that the IA-LSCS algorithm significantly improves localization accuracy compared to range-free DV-hop and range-based Kernel-based methods.

Qian et al. [44] in (2015) developed a two-stage procedure for multiple target detection and power estimation in WSNs, comprising an offline step and an online phase. This study is notable for localizing targets without prior knowledge of their transmitting capacities, unlike previous research using CS. In the offline stage, a sensing matrix is constructed by collecting RSSI readings from RF emitters. During the online phase, a restricted set of RSS data is used to accurately reconstruct a sparse vector. Both phases utilize M RF emitters and M sensors deployed randomly. Simulation results demonstrate that the proposed method is robust against measurement noise and

achieves high accuracy in target localization and power estimation.

Li et al. [45] in (2020) introduced a two-stage multi-target localization method based on the CS combined with the VD-TMTL. The Greedy Matching Pursuit algorithm, utilizing Voronoi Diagrams, is applied to identify candidate networks in local sub-regions. During the fine localization stage, these candidate grids are further subdivided into smaller grids according to the Least Grid Side Length hypothesis to enhance localization accuracy. Simulation results demonstrate that the VD-TMTL method significantly reduces response time while achieving high localization accuracy.

The authors of [41–43, 45] note that the number of operative sensors often depends on the total number of targets, a parameter that is typically unknown in advance. Moreover, the assumption made in [41–43] that both targets and sensor nodes are positioned at grid points is unrealistic in practical scenarios. Critically, all CS-based techniques [41–45] aim to reduce the number of active sensors by designating a subset for target sensing activities. However, this selection process requires centralized coordination, leading to increased power consumption for the sensors. Furthermore, the reduction in the number of active sensors does not necessarily extend the lifespan of WSNs, as there is no corresponding decrease in the number of bits per target detected by the active sensors. This limitation suggests that the energy savings achieved through sensor selection may be offset by the overhead associated with centralized control and data processing.

Table 1.2: Summary Comparison of CS-based Methods for Target Localization in WSNs

Reference	Approach	Algorithm	Advantages	Limitations
Feng et al. [41]	Target localization using RSSI measurements	Discretization of region into grid points	High localization accuracy with minimal RSSI observations	Assumes targets and sensors are on grid points
Liu et al. [42]	Range-free algorithm using binary sensors	MTLCS with SS sensor nodes	Improved localization accuracy without distance measurements	Localization error increases with the number of targets
Xin et al. [43]	Detection of multiple targets	Iterative Activation (IA) and IA-LSCS	Continuous monitoring with bandwidth and energy conservation	Centralized control increases power consumption
Qian et al. [44]	Multiple target detection and power estimation	Two-stage procedure (offline and online)	High accuracy in target localization and power estimation	Requires RSSI readings from RF emitters
Li et al. [45]	Multi-target localization using VD-TMTL	Greedy Matching Pursuit with Voronoi Diagrams	High localization accuracy and reduced response time	Requires central coordination, increasing power consumption

1.4.2 Off grid-Target Detection via WSNs

Yang et al. [46] in (2012) aimed to reduce modelling errors by exploring an off-grid model that accounts for the effects of off-grid DOAs. This method utilizes an iterative approach based on a Bayesian framework, leveraging joint sparsity across multiple snapshots with a Laplace prior for signals. This technique applies to both single-snapshot and multi-snapshot scenarios. Numerical simulations demonstrate that the proposed method enhances accuracy, as indicated by a reduction in mean squared estimation error. Furthermore, the technique maintains high estimation accuracy even with a highly coarse sampling grid.

Sun et al. [37] in 2016: The authors address the challenges of off-grid target localization and counting in WSNs. They propose an architecture that estimates the

sparsifying dictionary using a first-order Taylor expansion and frames the problem as a sparse recovery task. A variational Bayesian expectation-maximization approach is used to solve it. Simulations show that this method reduces localization error and improves target counting accuracy.

Guo et al. [47] in (2017): introduce an advanced sparse approximation paradigm for counting and localization. They estimate the unknown sparsifying dictionary around a known dictionary using a first-order Taylor expansion. The problem is framed as recovering two sparse signals with correlated supports, addressed using an iterative variational Bayesian inference method. To account for limited prior knowledge, such as coarse locations, a three-level hierarchical prior model is applied. Matrix inversion and grid-trimming techniques are also employed to expedite the inference. Simulation results show that this approach achieves superior accuracy and cost-efficiency in counting and localization compared to existing methods.

Wang et al. [35] in (2018): The authors present a robust sparse Bayesian learning technique for off-grid DoA estimation under irregular noise. Their method uses a modified inverse iteration to reconstruct the covariance matrix of non-uniform noise, with grid point locations refined iteratively through expectation-maximization and polynomial equation solutions. Simulations show that this technique achieves excellent DOA estimation accuracy even with uniform and non-uniform noise and performs well with poor grid resolution.

Qin et al. [36] in 2018: explore underdetermined wideband DOA estimation using the SBL with co-prime array setups. Co-prime arrays enhance the number of DOFs by resolving more sources than the physical sensors present, achieved through an improved covariance matrix. However, dictionary mismatch, where sources may be off the search grid, can impair sparse-based DOA estimation performance. The SBL approach addresses this issue effectively by automatically adjusting sparsity and nearly solving the non-convex optimization problem through fixed-point updates. Numerical simulations confirm that SBL with co-prime arrays outperforms other methods, such as the OGSBI, LASSO, SOMP-TLS, and SOMP-LS, in terms of both detection and estimation accuracy.

Guo et al. [38] in (2019): addresses the challenge of off-grid target localization using quantized measurements with bit-wise accuracy limitations. They propose a novel localization algorithm that leverages the VBEM approach to estimate target locations and mitigate quantization errors. This innovative application of the VBEM effectively addresses issues arising from quantized measurements in target localization. Simulation results demonstrate that the proposed algorithm outperforms existing methods, offering enhanced accuracy and robustness in scenarios with limited measurement precision.

Table 1.3: Summary Comparison of Off-Grid Targets Detection Methods in WSNs.

Reference	Method	Advantages	Results
Yang et al. [46] (2012)	Iterative Bayesian Framework with Joint Sparsity	Reduces modelling errors, maintains high accuracy even with coarse grid sampling	Improved estimation accuracy, reduced mean squared estimation error
Sun et al. [37] (2016)	Dictionary Estimation using First-Order Taylor Expansion	Reduces localization error, improves target counting accuracy	Enhanced localization and counting accuracy
Guo et al. [47] (2017)	Sparse Approximation Paradigm with Known Dictionary, Three-Level Hierarchical Prior Model	Superior accuracy and cost-efficiency in counting and localization	Superior accuracy and cost-efficiency compared to existing methods
Wang et al. [35] (2018)	Robust Sparse Bayesian Learning with Modified Inverse Iteration	Good DOA estimation accuracy, effective with non-uniform noise and poor grid resolution	Good DOA estimation accuracy with low-resolution grids
Qin et al. [36] (2018)	Underdetermined Wideband DOA Estimation using Co-Prime Arrays	Enhanced Degrees of Freedom, addresses dictionary mismatch effectively	Outperforms other methods in detection and estimation accuracy
Guo et al. [38] (2019)	Localization Algorithm with VBEM Approach	Mitigates quantization errors, improves localization accuracy and robustness	Outperforms existing methods in accuracy and robustness under limited measurement precision

1.4.3 Energy Consumption in WSNs

Min et al. [50] in (2010): propose a parameter-optimized clustering technique aimed at reducing energy consumption and enhancing system lifetime. The technique incorporates an analytical model considering one-hop distance and clustering angle. Optimal values for these parameters are determined to minimize energy usage both within and between clusters. Also, they describe a continuous operation process where each CH functions as a local control center, operating until optimal durations are achieved. This approach minimizes cluster head updates and associated energy costs. Simulation results confirm that the technique effectively lowers energy consumption and extends the system's lifetime.

Beiranvand et al. [51] in (2013) propose an energy-efficient routing method designed to conserve inter-network transmission energy in WSNs. The method prioritizes CH nodes based on their proximity to the base station (BS), number of neighbours, and residual energy. It aims to maximize WSN lifetime and minimize average energy dissipation per node by efficiently managing sensor nodes and forming clusters. Simulations conducted with a MATLAB simulator demonstrate that the proposed routing method significantly outperforms previous algorithms, including LEACH, DBS, and LEACH-C, achieving up to 65% better performance, reducing energy consumption by up to 62%, and increasing the successful packet delivery ratio by at least 56%.

Aldeer et al. [52] in 2016: The objective of the paper is to minimise energy consumption in transmit-only WSNs. To do this, it presents the issue as a convex optimisation problem that a SOCP solver can effectively solve. The main goal is to figure out where in the deployment field to put cluster head nodes to minimize energy consumption and meet the network's coverage and connectivity requirements. The results of the simulation show that using the optimization-based strategy reduces energy consumption by (16% – 24%) when compared to traditional placement techniques.

Farahzadi et al. [53] in (2021) propose an approach based on LEACH and Quadrant Cluster-based LEACH (Q-LEACH) protocols. This method divides the network into multiple zones and forms clusters within each zone to reduce energy consumption and enhance coverage. The base station determines the cluster head (CH) for each zone by evaluating the residual energy and distance from the center of each active node. The node with the highest combined value is selected as the CH for that area. By handling CH selection and distribution centrally, the base station reduces the computational burden on individual nodes. The protocol follows the information propagation

stages of LEACH. Simulations using MATLAB demonstrate that this approach outperforms LEACH, LEACHSWDN, and Q-LEACH in terms of first-node death time, last-node death time, and overall network lifetime.

Dhahir and Al Hilli [33] in 2023 proposed a CS mechanism for multi-target detection. The TOA measurements are employed by the algorithm to ensure the quantity and positions of targets. In this method the data transmission volume is efficiently reduced by reducing the number of bits and the number of transmission operations throughout the network is minimized. The sensors send a single packet containing information about every target to the CH. Therefore, increases in the sensors' lifetime in the WSNs are achieved in this approach. The simulations' results show the suggested method saves a substantial amount of energy while saving the target detection accuracy even in situations with a sizable number of targets.

Table 1.4: Summary Comparison of Energy Consumption Methods in WSNs

Reference	Method	Advantages	Results
Min et al. [50] (2010)	Parameter-optimized clustering technique	Reduces energy consumption, enhances system lifetime	Effectively lowers energy consumption and extends system lifetime
Beiranvand et al. [51] (2013)	Energy-efficient routing method	Maximizes WSN lifetime, minimizes average energy dissipation per node	Outperforms LEACH, DBS, and LEACH-C by up to 65% in performance
Aldeer et al. [52] (2016)	Optimization-based cluster head placement	Minimizes energy consumption, ensures coverage and connectivity	Reduces energy consumption by 16% - 24% compared to traditional techniques
Farahzadi et al. [53] (2021)	LEACH and Q-LEACH based approach	Reduces energy consumption, enhances coverage	Outperforms LEACH, LEACHSWDN, and Q-LEACH in terms of network lifetime
Dhahir and Al Hilli [33] (2023)	CS mechanism for multi-target detection using TOA measurements	Reduces data transmission volume, increases sensor lifetime	Saves substantial energy while maintaining target detection accuracy

Table 1.5: Comparative Table between On-Grid and Off-Grid Targets in WSNs

Aspect	On-Grid Targets	Off-Grid Targets
Definition	Targets are located directly on pre-defined grid points.	Targets located between pre-defined grid points.
Energy Consumption	Requires less energy due to easier location determination on grid points.	Requires more energy due to complex calculations for precise location determination.
Detection Accuracy	High accuracy in location determination due to reliance on predefined points.	Lower accuracy due to errors resulting from target displacement between grid points.
Complexity	Lower complexity since calculations are based on known and fixed points.	Higher complexity due to the need to compute and correct errors in target locations.
Detection Performance	High detection performance with a low probability of false alarms.	Good detection performance but with a higher probability of false alarms.
Techniques Used	Utilizes simple algorithms for on-grid point detection.	Requires advanced algorithms to handle off-grid errors and corrections.
Resource Utilization	Efficient resource usage due to predictable target locations.	Less efficient resource usage due to additional computations needed for off-grid targets.
Scalability	Easily scalable as target locations are fixed and predictable.	Less scalable due to the increased complexity of handling off-grid targets.
Robustness	More robust to environmental changes due to fixed target locations.	Less robust as it requires adaptive methods to handle variability in target positions.
Sensors configuration	Standard sensor configurations suffice.	Requires more flexible and adaptive sensor configurations.

1.5 Objective

In response to the identified challenges, this study aims to:

1. Develop an enhanced algorithm to improve the accuracy of multiple off-grid target localization in WSNs simultaneously, addressing the specific complexities and limitations of existing approaches.
2. Proposes and simulates strategies to reduce energy consumption, aiming to significantly extend the operational lifetime of network sensors.

1.6 Contributions

The contributions list includes the following key points:

1. Develop an enhanced approach to significantly increase the number of targets simultaneously detected by leveraging SBL in conjunction with CS theory.
2. Identify a sophisticated algorithmic approach designed to effectively address and resolve the challenges associated with off-grid target localization.
3. Develop and present an approach to significantly reduce energy consumption in WSNs by minimizing the number of sensors required for target detection through the application of A-SBL.

1.7 Organization of Thesis

The present work is organized as follows:

- **Chapter two:** This chapter gives background information on the algorithms employed in the study as well as a brief explanation of the WSNs in terms of mathematics and network models. These methods include the off-grid target addressing, the BP approach, the Multilateration method, the CS, and extending the lifetime of the WSNs' Sensors.
- **Chapter three:** It includes the proposed model for providing extensive mathematical models for enhancing target detection, addressing off-grid target problems and minimising energy consumption in the WSNs' sensors.
- **Chapter four:** It contains the simulation results for the Proposed Approaches to improve target detection through the suggested SBL method and compares it with both the BP and the traditional Multilateration approaches that are described in chapter.2. Also, the results of the suggested A-SBL method compared to the Multilateration approach in terms of less energy consumption and extended sensor lifetime.
- **Chapter five:** The suggested model's summary conclusions and recommendations for further research are presented in this chapter.

CHAPTER 2

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

This chapter advances background details for the algorithms that are employed in the work as well as an overview of the WSNs in terms of mathematics and system models. These methods include the multilateration approach, the CS theory, and the SBL.

2.1 Overview of the WSN

A large number of inexpensive, small active sensor nodes that are usually scattered randomly in a two-dimensional field make up the WSNs [54]. Data can be sensed, processed, and sent to the CH by each sensor node.

Target detection is an essential WSN service for security applications like tracking animal movements and recognising adversaries and intruders [55]. One may also consider target detection to be the initial stage of locating and tracking a moving target. Following a mobile target is necessary for some applications, such as those that monitor wildfires, dangerous gases, oil spills, and traffic management, to keep following the selected target over a large area [56].

The ToA, TDoA, AoA, and RSSI are common measures that are used in the Target detection [57]. In real-world situations, the RSS approach is less accurate than the

TOA and the TDOA techniques [58]. Additionally, the RSSI/AoA measurements are obtained from the signals produced by the targets; in non-cooperative contexts, such as military applications, these measurements cannot be linked to the targets that initially produced them. Target detection uses the ToA to identify the presence and count of targets by having all active sensors within the monitoring field emit signals with equal strength and measuring the round-trip journey time. By using the reflected signals from the objects, localization methods based on the ToA approach the location issue as an estimate of distance.

Sensors can be separated into two groups according to how they function: active sensors and passive sensors. The signals are produced and sent to the monitoring field by an active sensor, which then receives the signal that is sent out after reflecting off the target. The signal strength that the physical target emits is measured by the passive sensor. As opposed to active sensors, passive sensors do not transmit signals [59].

The sensor is composed of a sensing device, a processor and a radio or a communication unit that is employed to transmit the data it gathers from the sensors to a central unit known as the CH [60]. Before sending the data to the recipient, the CH analyses the information it has received from the network's sensors. Compared to all of the sensors in its sensing area, CH has the highest processing power as well as energy [61].

Energy consumption is a crucial factor to take into account in the WSNs for a variety of tasks. Generally speaking, three main elements contribute to the energy consumed by sensor nodes: (a) the energy consumption of the sensing unit, (b) the energy consumption of the processing unit, and (c) the energy consumption of the communication unit [5]. Interestingly, data transmission (via the communication unit)

uses more energy than both sensing and computing put together. Research shows that a sensor node's communicating unit uses around 80% of its energy [62].

The free-space energy model may be used to describe the energy used by the i^{th} sensor node, also known as E_{TX}^i , to send a packet containing B -bits of data to the CH across a communication channel as follows:[52, 61]:

$$E_{TX}^i = (\tau + v \times d_{CH,i}^\psi) \times B \quad (2.1)$$

Where $d_{CH,i}$ is the distance separated between the i^{th} sensor and CH, τ in J/bit and v in $J/(m \times bit)$ are fixed values conforming to the sending as well as receiving circuit, B denotes the number of transmitted bits and $\psi \in [2, 6]$ is the exponent of free-space [52].

As in [63], the sensor nodes function as limited energy devices in a difficult deployment environment where battery replacement or recharging is unfeasible. When a sensor runs out of battery power and fails operationally, it leaves a gap in the network that prevents the entire monitoring area's targets from being fully detected. The lifespan of the WSNs' sensors is one of the most important criteria used to assess their energy efficiency. The measurement of this indicator is the number of rounds that sensors provide data to a fusion centre until the first sensor fails [61, 64]. Various methods, such as clustering, are used to reduce energy consumption in the WSNs. Clustering involves dividing the network into sections, each overseen by the CH. This organizational approach enhances energy efficiency by assigning specific responsibilities to individual cluster heads, as illustrated in [65].

2.2 Multilateration Approach

Assuming an area of dimensions $(L \times L)$ for the monitoring scenario, targets can appear anywhere in the monitoring region. The Static sensor nodes are dispersed at random throughout the monitoring area, with the CH situated in the centre. The precise locations of these sensor nodes are determined through self-localization techniques that utilize GPS[66]. By designating the sensor nodes as $i = 1, 2, \dots, S$, and denoting the coordinates of each node as $s_i = (x_i, y_i)$, the nodes can measure the distances that they have to the targets that are scattered across the monitoring area. Localizing and detecting targets is made easier by utilizing this distance data in combination with the locations of known sensor nodes. The Multilateration method has been used in the standard methodology [40] for target detection, commonly used in the WSNs. When m targets appear concurrently in the monitoring field, each sensor node uses ToA to measure the distances to all m targets whose positions are unknown (x_a, y_a) . It then transmits this information to the CH. This method uses sensors to send data specific to each target separately [40].

$$\begin{bmatrix} d_1^2 \\ d_2^2 \\ \vdots \\ d_s^2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} (x_1 - x_a)^2 + (y_1 - y_a)^2 \\ (x_2 - x_a)^2 + (y_1 - y_a)^2 \\ \vdots \\ (x_s - x_a)^2 + (y_s - y_a)^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.2)$$

A linear system is created by converting the nonlinear distance equation to get the target's place in the CH. The terms can be adjusted to generate the following system of linear equations [40]:

$$Kx = t \quad (2.3)$$

In which the coefficients matrix $\mathbf{K} \in R^{(S-1) \times 2}$ is determined employing sensor coordinates and has the following definition:

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{bmatrix} 2(x_S - x_1) & 2(y_S - y_1) \\ 2(x_S - x_2) & 2(y_S - y_2) \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ 2(x_S - x_{S-1}) & 2(y_S - y_{S-1}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.4)$$

and the distance vector $\mathbf{t} \in R^{(S-1) \times 1}$ is represented as follows:

$$\mathbf{t} = \begin{bmatrix} d_1^2 - d_S^2 - x_1^2 - y_1^2 + x_S^2 + y_S^2 \\ d_2^2 - d_S^2 - x_2^2 - y_2^2 + x_S^2 + y_S^2 \\ \vdots \\ d_{S-1}^2 - d_S^2 - x_{S-1}^2 - y_{S-1}^2 + x_S^2 + y_S^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.5)$$

The following is an estimate of the target's final two-dimensional location:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}} = (\mathbf{K}^T \mathbf{K})^{-1} \mathbf{K}^T \mathbf{t} \quad (2.6)$$

For every target, the previously explained method is repeatedly applied iteratively. Regardless of the quantity and locations of the targets, the multilateration technique yields an accurate estimation of their positions. One of the primary problems with the WSN, though, is that the quantity of data transfer required to detect many targets can have a significant impact on the network's lifetime.

2.3 Compressed Sensing (CS) Theory

In recent years, there has been a notable rise in interest and application of CS among researchers across diverse fields. These include image processing, medical imaging, target detection in military applications, array processing and DOA estimation, as well as MIMO radar systems for target detection. [26, 67, 68]. Target detection using particular datasets has been the application of the CS theory in more recent times. When certain requirements are met, such as mutual coherence, Nullspace Property (NSP), Restricted Isometry Property (RIP) and Range Space Property (RSP), CS shows that it can reconstruct sparse signals with fewer samples than Nyquist sampling [69, 70]. By minimising the quantity of data that is required to be processed, the CS application seeks to lower energy consumption in the WSNs and speed up the data processing [71].

By employing lower random measures, the CS operates. The CS problem can thus be expressed as follows, as illustrated in Figure 2.1:

$$\mathbf{y} = \Phi \mathbf{x} \quad (2.7)$$

When the signal input is $\mathbf{x} \in R^N$. The random measurement matrix is $\Phi \in R^{M \times N}$, while the measurement vector is $\mathbf{y} \in R^M$. The random measurement matrix is multiplied by the input signal to create compressive measurements. The number of measurements is less than the length of the input signal ($M \ll N$). The size of the measurement matrix and, consequently, the total number of measurements, are directly correlated with the sparsity of the input signal. To further minimize the number of measurements required for precise reconstruction, the measurement matrix has to be incoherent with the basis where the signal is represented sparsely [73, 74].

Figure 2.1: The CS Model [72].

A basic stage in the CS reconstructing techniques is recovering vector \mathbf{x} from the measurement vector \mathbf{y} and measurement matrix Φ . To reconstitute the original data after it has been compressed, a set of underdetermined equations must be solved. For \mathbf{x} , there are an unlimited number of alternative solutions. Usually, the best candidate is found by minimising the ℓ_0 norm of \mathbf{x} [75].

$$\underset{\mathbf{x}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \|\mathbf{x}\|_0 \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \mathbf{y} = \Phi \mathbf{x} \quad (2.8)$$

ℓ_0 has been the optimal solution, however, it is extremely noise-sensitive (easily satisfied by noise) because all that is needed to get the answer is to discover all nonzero elements.

In summary, unlike the traditional sensing systems, which sample data at a predetermined pace. The CS uses the sparsity of perceived signals to provide an alternate method. Many applications exhibit sparse structural properties in the data, allowing important information to be obtained with fewer relevant observations. As a result, the CS offers an energy-efficient strategy that enhances the lifetime of the WSNs. [26–28]

2.4 Basis Pursuit (BP) approach

The BP approach [33] is one of the methods that successfully use the CS to reduce energy consumption while showing good performance for localization and detection of target locations. It is based on approximating the ℓ_0 norm to the ℓ_1 norm. By assuming that have a $R \times R$ dimensional field that is divided into N grid points that are spaced as uniform, represented by the notation $j = 1, 2, \dots, N$. $g_j = (x_j, y_j)$ represents a coordinate for each grid point. There exist m on-grid targets in this sensing area. Furthermore, there is just one CH that is positioned in the middle of the sensing area. Static sensors are dispersed at random over the area of observation. The sensor nodes' locations, indicated by $i = 1, 2, \dots, S$, are known and can be found using self-localization techniques or GPS [66]. When the sensor nodes wake up, they use TOA to report their relative distances to all m targets. For every sensor node, this data is combined into a vector $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^{S \times 1}$, which is subsequently sent to the CH as follows:

$$z_i = \sum_{h=1, \dots, m} d_{i,h}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, S \quad (2.9)$$

where $\sum_{h=1, \dots, m}$ denotes that each sensor will aggregate the distances to all targets as the $d_{i,h}$ represent the distance from n^{th} sensor to h^{th} target and the on-grid targets' number is denoted by m . The measurement matrix $\mathbf{D} \in R^{S \times N}$ is created by the CH. The coordinates of the grid points and sensor nodes are used to calculate every element in this matrix as follows:

$$\mathbf{D} = \begin{bmatrix} d_{11} & \dots & d_{1N} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ d_{S1} & \dots & d_{SN} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.10)$$

The linear system can be generated as the following system of linear equations [33]:

$$z = Dq \quad (2.11)$$

Given the sparsity constraints, the BP is used to recover the target vector $q \in R^{N \times 1}$ by solving the following ℓ_1 -norm problem:

$$\underset{q}{\text{minimize}} \quad \|q\|_1 \quad \text{subject to} \quad z = Dq \quad (2.12)$$

For the ℓ_1 norm, the BP, which uses global optimisation, can achieve stable super-resolution [76]. Sparsity is promoted by ℓ_1 minimization due to the geometric shape of the ℓ_1 balls, which are diamond-shaped. This shape encourages sparse solutions by favouring many coefficients to be zero. Figure 2.2 shows the comparative of ℓ_1 and ℓ_2 minimization, which indicates how ℓ_1 minimization enhances sparsity. The ROMP [77], BPDN [78], and the OMP [79] are further recovery techniques. When compared to other methodologies, BP is the most often used linear programming technique [80].

Although the BP can effectively detect targets and lower the energy needed for detection, it is imprecise and its algorithms fail down when there are a lot of targets. Also, it is ineffective in off-grid target settings. In the following sections, methods are presented CS-based that enhance the number of detected targets, address off-grid target issues, and extend the lifetime of WSNs sensors without compromising detection quality [34, 46, 82].

Figure 2.2: The ℓ_1 minimization versus the ℓ_2 minimization
[81]

2.5 Sparse Bayesian Learning (SBL).

To model complicated data with high-dimensional feature spaces and encourage sparsity in the model parameters, the SBL is a potent machine learning paradigm. To handle large-scale datasets efficiently and lessen the effects of dimensions, it integrates the ideas of Bayesian inference with methods for generating sparsity. Representations of Sparse signals derived from over-complete dictionaries are becoming more and more relevant in many different application domains. Obtaining such representations also amounts to resolving regularized linear inverse problems, which are widely relevant in the fields of feature extraction, compression, and signal processing. Thus, it is crucial to gain a greater understanding of these problems from a theoretical and practical standpoint. The standard version of this issue is provided as follows [82]:

$$y = \Phi w + e \quad (2.13)$$

where $\mathbf{w} \in R^{N \times 1}$ is adjustable parameters or the vector of weights to be learned, \mathbf{e} is noise, and $\mathbf{y} \in R^{S \times 1}$ is a vector of targets. The matrix $\Phi \in R^{S \times N}$ has columns that indicate a potentially over-complete basis (i.e., rank S and $N > S$), where S represents the number of sensor nodes, and N denotes the number of grid points. Similarly, the objective is to estimate the sparse weight vectors that facilitate accurate estimation of \mathbf{y} , while predominantly having zero elements. Using the fewest possible basis vectors to express \mathbf{y} is the equivalent of this[34, 82].

The SBL can be employed to estimate the weight vector. Sparsity in the context of the SBL refers to the existence of only a small number of non-zero values in the model. In the SBL, the weight vector \mathbf{w} can be modelled as an independent multivariate Gaussian random vector with random entries with mean zero and variance α_i^{-1} , as follows:

$$P(\mathbf{w}|\boldsymbol{\alpha}) = \prod_{i=0}^N \mathcal{N}(w_i|0, \alpha_i^{-1}) \quad (2.14)$$

$$P(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) = \prod_{i=0}^N \Gamma(\alpha_i|a, b) \quad (2.15)$$

$$P(\sigma^{-2}) = \Gamma(\sigma^{-2}|c, d) \quad (2.16)$$

Where $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ is a vector representing the hyper-parameters. Notably, each weight is associated independently with an individual hyper-parameter [34]. Γ is a gamma distribution and σ^2 is the hyper-parameter for noise variance. Shape (a and c) and rate (b and d) parameters are commonly used to describe the Gamma distribution [83]. An even more noticeable distribution with a possible zero-skewing can be obtained with larger values of the shape parameter (a). The distribution may widen in the interim with higher values of the rate parameter b .

Bayesian inference, which offers a logical framework for probabilistic modelling and inference, is the foundation of the SBL. By applying Bayes' theorem, it is possible to revise assumptions about model parameters in Bayesian inference based on observed data, thereby updating the posterior distributions of all unknowns following the available data[34]:

$$p(\mathbf{w}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \sigma^2 | \mathbf{y}) = \frac{p(\mathbf{y} | \mathbf{w}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \sigma^2) p(\mathbf{w}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \sigma^2)}{p(\mathbf{y})} \quad (2.17)$$

The posterior $p(\mathbf{w}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \sigma^2 | \mathbf{y})$ in 2.17 cannot be computed directly since the normalizing integral on the right-hand side $p(\mathbf{y}) = \int p(\mathbf{y} | \mathbf{w}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \sigma^2) p(\mathbf{w} | \boldsymbol{\alpha}) p(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) d\mathbf{w} d\boldsymbol{\alpha} d\sigma^2$ cannot be performed. Rather, the posterior is broken down as follows [34]:

$$p(\mathbf{w}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \sigma^2 | \mathbf{y}) = p(\mathbf{w} | \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \sigma^2, \mathbf{y}) p(\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \sigma^2 | \mathbf{y}) \quad (2.18)$$

Since the normalizing integral, $p(\mathbf{y} | \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \sigma^2) = \int p(\mathbf{y} | \mathbf{w}, \sigma^2) p(\mathbf{w} | \boldsymbol{\alpha}) d\mathbf{w}$, is a Gaussian convolution, allowing us to calculate the posterior distribution over the weights analytically. Therefore, the following represents the posterior distribution over the weights [34]:

$$p(\mathbf{w} | \mathbf{y}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \sigma^2) = \frac{p(\mathbf{y} | \mathbf{w}, \sigma^2) p(\mathbf{w} | \boldsymbol{\alpha})}{p(\mathbf{y} | \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \sigma^2)}, \quad (2.19)$$

Then,

$$p(\mathbf{w} | \mathbf{y}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \sigma^2) = (2\pi)^{-(N+1)/2} |\boldsymbol{\Sigma}|^{-1/2} \times \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{w} - \boldsymbol{\mu})^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{-1} (\mathbf{w} - \boldsymbol{\mu}) \right\} \quad (2.20)$$

From (2.14), the weight's posterior density function with mean $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ and covariance ma-

trix Σ can be written as follows [34]:

$$\Sigma = (\sigma^{-2}\Phi^T\Phi + \Lambda)^{-1} \quad (2.21)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\mu} = \sigma^{-2}\Sigma\Phi^T\mathbf{y} \quad (2.22)$$

where $\Lambda = \text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\alpha})$, $\boldsymbol{\alpha} = [\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_N]^T$. One can see that to use such an estimate, we need to estimate the values of $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ and σ^2 . In the SBL, the mode (i.e., the maximum) of the hyper-parameters posterior is used. This posterior is proportional to the product of the marginal likelihood and hyper-parameters priors. Furthermore, it can be shown that the marginal likelihood follows a Gaussian distribution[34], with probability density function (PDF) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} P(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \sigma^2) &= (2\pi)^{-\frac{N}{2}} |\sigma^2\mathbf{I} + \Phi\Lambda^{-1}\Phi^T|^{-\frac{1}{2}} \\ &\times \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2}\mathbf{y}^T(\sigma^2\mathbf{I} + \Phi\Lambda^{-1}\Phi^T)^{-1}\mathbf{y} \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (2.23)$$

Differentiating hyper-parameter posterior with respect to $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ and equating to zero [34] yields :

$$\alpha_i = \frac{1 + 2a}{\boldsymbol{\mu}_i^2 + \Sigma_{ii}^2 + 2b} \quad (2.24)$$

Differentiating the posterior with respect to σ^2 and equating to zero [34] yields

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{\|\mathbf{t} - \Phi\boldsymbol{\mu}\|^2 + 2d}{N - \sum_i \gamma_i + 2c} \quad (2.25)$$

where the quantity $\gamma_i \equiv 1 - \alpha_i\Sigma_{ii}$.

Once α and σ^2 are calculated using (2.24) and (2.25) by maximising the posterior distribution of hyper-parameters. While μ and Σ are determined by looking at the expectation of the posterior distribution over the weights in (2.14). The value of w that corresponds to the maximum probability represents the estimated weight.

Since the ℓ_0 norm can be approximated more accurately using the SBL approach from the ℓ_1 norm as the BP [33], furthermore, the SBLs' cavity tends to be smoother and more curved than that of the BP method. Also, the off-grid problem is easily addressed by the SBL approaches with high efficiency. nevertheless, while it has an issue due to the non-convexity problem, many studies have shown that the SBL is better than the ℓ_1 norm [34]

2.6 Off-grid DOA Estimation Using Sparse Bayesian Inference approach

This technique [46] uses the off-grid model that works well in the SMV and Multiple Measurement Vector (MMV) settings to provide a Bayesian approach for DOA estimates. This approach assumes that the off-grid distance, which is the difference between the genuine DOA and the closest grid point, follows a uniform distribution inside a predetermined interval and is hence considered non-informative [46]. The technique first determines the sparse weights vector's mean and covariance matrix, according to the Bayesian methodology described in Section 2.5. The next steps include using the Bayesian mode to compute the displacements between the actual targets and the grid points that are closest to them.

The on-grid model is the approximation of the zeroth-order of the genuine observation model, whereas the off-grid model can be thought of as the approximation of the first-order. Because of this, compared to the on-grid model, the off-grid model has a far

lower modelling error. There are two benefits to this. First, the off-grid model achieves higher accuracy by using the same sample grid; this is particularly true when there is little measurement noise and the modelling error is the main modelling uncertainty. Secondly, to obtain a significantly lower computing workload with a comparable modelling accuracy, a coarser sampling grid might be used in the off-grid model [46].

Consider of an array of M omni-directional sensors that are being impinged upon by K narrow-band far-field sources $s_k(t)$, $k = 1, \dots, K$, from directions θ_k , $k = 1, \dots, K$. Simple phase shifts can be used to represent time delays at various sensors [84], which leads to the observance model:

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \Phi(\theta)\mathbf{s}(t) + \mathbf{e}(t), \quad t = 1, \dots, T, \quad (2.26)$$

In which $\mathbf{y}(t) = [y_1(t), \dots, y_M(t)]^T \in R^{M \times 1}$, $\boldsymbol{\theta} = [\theta_1, \dots, \theta_K]^T$, $\mathbf{s}(t) = [s_1(t), \dots, s_K(t)]^T \in R^{K \times 1}$, and $\mathbf{e}(t) = [e_1(t), \dots, e_M(t)]^T \in R^{M \times 1}$. Here, the m^{th} sensor's output and measurement noise at time t are denoted by the variables $y_m(t)$ and $e_m(t)$, $m = 1, \dots, M$, respectively. $\Phi(\theta) = [\mathbf{a}(\theta_1), \dots, \mathbf{a}(\theta_K)] \in R^{M \times K}$ describes the matrix that is an array manifold matrix, and the steering vector of the k^{th} source is denoted as $\mathbf{a}(\theta_k)$. The k^{th} source's delay information to the m^{th} sensor is contained in the entry $\mathbf{a}_m(\theta_k)$. The sources' number K is assumed to be known before using this strategy. Regarding the scenario of unknown K , readers are directed to a preprint version for debate. Therefore, given K , $\mathbf{y}(t)$, and the mapping $\boldsymbol{\theta} \rightarrow \Phi(\theta)$, the objective is to discover the unknown DoAs ($\boldsymbol{\theta}$). The off-grid model's re-deriving is provided in the following utilising a linear approximation [85], and it also demonstrates how it relates to the on-grid model.

In the DoA range $[0, \pi]$, let $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}} = \{\tilde{\theta}_1, \dots, \tilde{\theta}_N\}$ be a fixed sample grid. The grid number N usually fulfils $N \gg M > K$. Let $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ represent a uniform grid with a grid interval of $s = \tilde{\theta}_2 - \tilde{\theta}_1 \propto N^{-1}$, without losing generality. Let $\tilde{\theta}_k \notin \{\tilde{\theta}_1, \dots, \tilde{\theta}_N\}$ for some $k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$, and be the nearest grid point to $\tilde{\theta}_k$, with $n_k \in \{1, \dots, N\}$. Using linearization, the steering vector $\mathbf{a}(\tilde{\theta}_k)$ is approximated as follows[46]:

$$\mathbf{a}(\tilde{\theta}_k) \approx \mathbf{a}(\tilde{\theta}_{n_k}) + \mathbf{b}(\tilde{\theta}_{n_k})(\theta_k - \tilde{\theta}_{n_k}) \quad (2.27)$$

with $\mathbf{b}(\tilde{\theta}_{n_k}) = \mathbf{a}'(\tilde{\theta}_{n_k})$. Denote $\mathbf{\Phi} = [\mathbf{a}(\tilde{\theta}_1), \dots, \mathbf{a}(\tilde{\theta}_N)]^T$, $\mathbf{B} = [\mathbf{b}(\tilde{\theta}_1), \dots, \mathbf{b}(\tilde{\theta}_N)]^T$, $\boldsymbol{\beta} = [\beta_1, \dots, \beta_N]^T \in \mathcal{U}(\frac{-S}{2}, \frac{S}{2})$, and $\mathbf{\Phi}(\boldsymbol{\beta}) = \mathbf{\Phi} + \mathbf{B}\text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$, where $\mathbf{B} \in R^{M \times N}$ matrix represent the derivatives of matrix $\mathbf{\Phi}$ with respect to the θ , and where $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is $\in R^{N \times 1}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \beta_n &= \theta_k - \tilde{\theta}_{n_k}, \\ w_n(t) &= s_{n_k}(t), \quad \text{if } n = n_k \text{ for any } k \in \{1, \dots, K\}; \\ \beta_n &= 0, \quad w_n(t) = 0 \text{ otherwise.} \end{aligned} \quad (2.28)$$

The closest grid to a source θ_k , $k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$, is $\tilde{\theta}_{n_k}$, and $n_k \in \{1, \dots, N\}$. In 2.26, the observation model may be expressed as follows by including the approximation error into the measurement noise:

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{\Phi}(\boldsymbol{\beta})\mathbf{w}(t) + \mathbf{e}(t), \quad t = 1, \dots, T, \quad (2.29)$$

The algorithm is derived in the MMV situation. $\mathbf{W} = [\mathbf{w}(1), \dots, \mathbf{w}(T)]$, $\mathbf{e} = [\mathbf{e}(1), \dots, \mathbf{e}(T)]$, and $\mathbf{Y} = [\mathbf{y}(1), \dots, \mathbf{y}(T)]$ are highlighted. Setting $T = 1$ allows us to consider the case of a single measurement vector, sometimes referred to as a single snapshot or

SMV. The off-grid DOA model From (2.29) to:

$$\mathbf{y} = \Phi(\boldsymbol{\beta})\mathbf{w} + \mathbf{e} \quad (2.30)$$

where $\Phi(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ is $\in R^{M \times N}$ is the measurements matrix with off-grid errors, In other words, it is a representation of the measurements as well as their displacements along the θ .

As described in Section 2.5, this technique relies on the Bayesian model to calculate the $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$. Afterwards, as stated in the lines that follow, $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is computed.

To model such displacements, $(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ is modelled as uniformly distributed $(\boldsymbol{\beta}) \sim \mathcal{U}(\frac{-S}{2}, \frac{S}{2})$. Since the prior in this case is considered non-informative, its boundedness serves as our only source of information. can obtain the joint probability density function (PDF) $P(\mathbf{w}, \mathbf{y}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \sigma^2, \boldsymbol{\beta})$ by integrating the varied of the Bayesian hierarchical model stages[46]. the joint distribution of $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is as follows:

$$P(\mathbf{w}, \mathbf{y}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \sigma^2, \boldsymbol{\beta}) = P(\mathbf{y}|\mathbf{w}, \boldsymbol{\beta})P(\mathbf{w}|\boldsymbol{\alpha})P(\boldsymbol{\alpha})P(\sigma^2)P(\boldsymbol{\beta}) \quad (2.31)$$

The optimal displacement can be obtained by maximizing the expected joint distribution. It can be shown that the expected value is[46]

$$E \{ \|\mathbf{y} - \Phi(\boldsymbol{\beta})\boldsymbol{\mu}\|^2 \} = \boldsymbol{\beta}^T \mathbf{P}\boldsymbol{\beta} - 2\mathbf{v}\boldsymbol{\beta} + M \quad (2.32)$$

where $\Phi(\boldsymbol{\beta}) = \Phi + \mathbf{B}\text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$, and M is a constant term resulting from the simpli-

fication and decomposition of $E \{ \|\mathbf{y} - \Phi(\boldsymbol{\beta})\boldsymbol{\mu}\|^2 \}$. The optimal value of $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is:

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}} = \arg \min_{\boldsymbol{\beta} \in (-\frac{S}{2}, \frac{S}{2})} [\boldsymbol{\beta}^T \mathbf{P} \boldsymbol{\beta} - 2\mathbf{v} \boldsymbol{\beta}] \quad (2.33)$$

where $\mathbf{P} \in R^{N \times N}$ is:

$$\mathbf{P} = \Re[\mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{B} \circ (\boldsymbol{\mu}^T \boldsymbol{\mu} + \boldsymbol{\Sigma})] \quad (2.34)$$

and $\mathbf{v} \in R^{N \times 1}$ is :

$$\mathbf{v} = \Re[\text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\mu}) \mathbf{B}^T (\mathbf{y} - \Phi \boldsymbol{\mu})] - \Re[\text{diag}(\mathbf{B}^T \Phi \boldsymbol{\Sigma})] \quad (2.35)$$

While \circ denotes matrix dot multiplication, the notation \Re denotes the determination of real values. By differentiating Eq.(2.33) with respect to $\boldsymbol{\beta}$, setting the derivative to zero, and solving for $\boldsymbol{\beta}$, the result is $\boldsymbol{\beta} = \mathbf{P}^{-1} \mathbf{v}$. When \mathbf{P} is invertible, $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ can be directly computed using this equation. However, in more general scenarios, $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is updated iteratively at each step as follows[46]:

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_n = \frac{(\mathbf{v})_n - (\mathbf{P}_n)_{-n}^T (\boldsymbol{\beta})_{-n}}{(\mathbf{P})_{(n,n)}}, n = 1, \dots, K. \quad (2.36)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{-n}$ denotes a vector without the n^{th} entry, then as the following:

$$\boldsymbol{\beta}_n^{\hat{new}} = \begin{pmatrix} \boldsymbol{\beta}_n, \text{ if } \boldsymbol{\beta}_n \in (-\frac{S}{2}, \frac{S}{2}) \\ -\frac{S}{2}, \text{ if } \boldsymbol{\beta}_n < -\frac{S}{2} \\ \frac{S}{2}, \text{ if } \boldsymbol{\beta}_n > \frac{S}{2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.37)$$

Using (2.37) to ensure that all values of β determined in (2.36) remain within the specified range $(-\frac{S}{2}, \frac{S}{2})$. Finally, we can determine that $\tilde{\theta}_k = \tilde{\theta}_{\tilde{n}k} + \tilde{\beta}_{\tilde{n}k}$, $k = 1, \dots, K$

CHAPTER 3

THE SIMULATIONS MODEL DESCRIPTION AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter provides extensive mathematical models for multi-target detection using the SBL employing the use of the CS theory to increase the number of the detected targets and address the off-grid target problems. It also presents an algorithm that is intended to maintain high detection levels in the WSNs while minimising energy consumption.

3.2 Proposed Approach for Targets Detection in the WSNs

A Sparse Bayesian method for estimating target location employing the CS shows improved performance in many applications, including the WSNs. In this section, the proposed methodology for target detection within the sensing area is presented. Thus, the proposed method is explained and described in two scenarios: One when the targets are on-grid and the other where the targets are off-grid.

3.2.1 On-Grid Location Estimation Model

Here, we consider N Sensors that are randomly scattered over the sensing area. The area of interest is divided into G equidistant grid points in both x and y directions. The sensors measure the distances to potential targets that are hypothetically located on the grid points. The readings from all sensors are then transmitted to CH. Then, the CH uses sensor readings to localize the targets. From the CH perspective, the system can be modelled as follows:

$$\mathbf{y} = \Phi \mathbf{w} + \mathbf{e} \quad (3.1)$$

Where $\mathbf{y} \in R^{N \times 1}$ is a vector of size N , and each entry corresponds to the sum of the relative target distances to the corresponding sensor location. $\Phi = [\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2, \dots, \mathbf{a}_G]$ is the measurement matrix $\in R^{N \times G}$. Each column $\mathbf{a}_g = [D_1, D_2, \dots, D_N]^T$ in Φ represents the distances from the N sensors to the g^{th} grid point, for $g = 1, \dots, G$. \mathbf{e} is the additive white Gaussian noise vector with mean zero and variance σ^2 , and \mathbf{w} represents the sparse weight vector $\in R^{G \times 1}$.

The goal is to estimate the weights vector \mathbf{w} , which represents The grid-points indicators that can be used to extract or determine the estimated targets' locations. Under sparsity constraints, the SBL can be employed to estimate the weight vector. The sparsity in the context of the SBL refers to the existence of only a small number of non-zero values in the model.

As a result, using the model mentioned in Section 2.5 from (2.20), we can compute and estimate the sparse weights vector \mathbf{w} during the computation of its mean μ_w and

covariance matrix $\Sigma_w \in R^{G \times G}$ according to (2.22) and (2.21) lead to as follows:

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_w = \sigma^{-2} \Sigma_w \Phi^T \mathbf{y} \quad (3.2)$$

$$\Sigma_w = (\sigma^{-2} \Phi^T \Phi + \Lambda)^{-1} \quad (3.3)$$

Moreover, we use (2.24) and (2.25) as mentioned in Section 2.5 to compute the required values of the hyper-parameters α and σ^2 for determining the mean and covariance matrix. Across eq.(3.2), the $\boldsymbol{\mu}_w \in R^{G \times 1}$ represents the estimated sparse weight vector, characterized by mostly zero values with relatively few non-zero elements. Accessing w thus entails accessing the target locations if the target is assumed to be on a presumptive grid point since the non-zero values can be used to deduce the coordinates of the grid points where the targets are located. The coordinates of the targets inside the sensing region can be accessed as these assumed grid points are initially known. The difficulty lies, instead, in the targets' ability to appear anywhere in the area, not just at the presumptive grid points. Therefore, it becomes necessary to locate these targets, also known as off-grid targets, which we shall discuss in the following subsection.

3.2.2 Off-Grid Location Estimation Model:

This subsection discusses the case of the off-grid target location estimation. The goal is to locate the nearest grid point from the target and determine the displacement values along the (x, y) axes in Cartesian coordinates. In this case, the displacement along x and y coordinates is calculated jointly rather than separately in the case of on-grid location estimation. The displacement errors can be obtained by maximizing the expected log-likelihood function along x and y coordinates jointly instead of separate

estimation as in [46]. From (3.1), we have

$$\mathbf{y} = \Phi_{(\Delta\mathbf{x}, \Delta\mathbf{y})} \mathbf{w} + e \quad (3.4)$$

Where $\Phi_{(\Delta\mathbf{x}, \Delta\mathbf{y})}$ is the measurements matrix with the off-grid errors, In other words, it is a representation of the measurements as well as their displacements along the x and y axes, respectively. Mathematically, $\Phi_{(\Delta\mathbf{x}, \Delta\mathbf{y})}$ can be modeled as follows:

$$\Phi_{(\Delta\mathbf{x}, \Delta\mathbf{y})} = \Phi + \mathbf{B} \text{diag}(\Delta\mathbf{x}) + \mathbf{C} \text{diag}(\Delta\mathbf{y}) \quad (3.5)$$

$\mathbf{B} \in R^{N \times G}$ and $\mathbf{C} \in R^{N \times G}$ matrices represent the derivatives of matrix Φ with respect to the x and y , respectively. Mathematically, $\mathbf{B} = [\mathbf{b}_1, \mathbf{b}_2, \dots, \mathbf{b}_G]$, $\mathbf{b}_g = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathbf{a}_g$ and $\mathbf{C} = [\mathbf{c}_1, \mathbf{c}_2, \dots, \mathbf{c}_G]$, $\mathbf{c}_g = \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \mathbf{a}_g$. These vectors can be rewritten as $\mathbf{b}_g = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [D_1, D_2, \dots, D_N]$ and $\mathbf{c}_g = \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [D_1, D_2, \dots, D_N]$, $(\Delta\mathbf{x}, \Delta\mathbf{y})$ are modelled as uniformly distributed random variables $(\Delta\mathbf{x}, \Delta\mathbf{y}) \sim \mathcal{U}(\frac{-S}{2}, \frac{S}{2})$, where S is the distance between any two adjacent grid points. And both $(\Delta\mathbf{x}, \Delta\mathbf{y})$ are $\in R^{G \times 1}$

Two off-grid cases are considered in this work regarding the dependency of the displacement errors along x and y directions:

B.1 Here, we assume that $(\Delta\mathbf{x}, \Delta\mathbf{y})$ are independent.

The joint distribution of $\Delta\mathbf{x}$ in this case can be estimated using the procedure given in Section 2.6 by applying the following equations; similarly to equations (2.31), (2.32), and (2.33) and where $\Phi_{\Delta\mathbf{x}} = \Phi + \mathbf{B} \text{diag}(\Delta\mathbf{x})$, we obtain:

$$\Delta\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{P}_x^{-1} \mathbf{v}_x \quad (3.6)$$

If (P_x) is inevitable, we can directly compute $\Delta \mathbf{x}$ using the equation above. However, in more general scenarios, we iteratively update the value at each step as follows[46]

$$\hat{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_g = \frac{(\mathbf{v}_x)_g - ((P_x)_g)^T (\Delta \mathbf{x})_{-g}}{(P_x)_{(g,g)}} \quad (3.7)$$

Then,

$$\Delta \hat{\mathbf{x}}_g^{new} = \begin{pmatrix} \Delta \mathbf{x}_g, \text{if } \Delta \mathbf{x}_g \in (-\frac{S}{2}, \frac{S}{2}) \\ -\frac{S}{2}, \text{if } \Delta \mathbf{x}_g < -\frac{S}{2} \\ \frac{S}{2}, \text{if } \Delta \mathbf{x}_g > \frac{S}{2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.8)$$

where $P_x \in R^{G \times G}$ as in (2.34) become $P_x = \Re[B^T B \circ (\boldsymbol{\mu}^T \boldsymbol{\mu} + \Sigma)]$, and $\mathbf{v}_x \in R^{G \times 1}$ as in (2.35) become $\mathbf{v}_x = \Re[\text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\mu}) B^T (\mathbf{y} - \Phi \boldsymbol{\mu})] - \Re[\text{diag}(B^T \Phi \Sigma)]$

Finally, to determine that the X-axis coordinate of any target is $X_t = X_g + \Delta \mathbf{x}$. where X_g is calculated by estimating the $\boldsymbol{\mu}_w$ in (3.2) on-grid.

By repeating the same procedure used on $\Delta \mathbf{x}$, $\Delta \mathbf{y}$ can be estimated while taking into account that the calculations for both matrix P and vector V are modified using the matrix C instead of matrix B and $\Phi_{\Delta \mathbf{y}} = \Phi + C \text{diag}(\Delta \mathbf{y})$, we get $\Delta \mathbf{y} = P_y^{-1} \mathbf{v}_y$. If (P_y) is inevitable and :

$$\hat{\Delta \mathbf{y}}_g = \frac{(\mathbf{v}_y)_g - ((P_y)_g)^T (\Delta \mathbf{y})_{-g}}{(P_y)_{(g,g)}} \quad (3.9)$$

$$\Delta \mathbf{y}_g^{\hat{new}} = \begin{pmatrix} \Delta \mathbf{y}_g, \text{if } \Delta \mathbf{y}_g \in (-\frac{S}{2}, \frac{S}{2}) \\ -\frac{S}{2}, \text{if } \Delta \mathbf{y}_g < -\frac{S}{2} \\ \frac{S}{2}, \text{if } \Delta \mathbf{y}_g > \frac{S}{2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.10)$$

where $\mathbf{P}_y = \Re[\mathbf{C}^T \mathbf{C} \circ (\boldsymbol{\mu}^T \boldsymbol{\mu} + \boldsymbol{\Sigma})]$, where $\mathbf{P}_y \in R^{G \times G}$, and

$\mathbf{v}_y = \Re[\text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\mu}) \mathbf{C}^T (\mathbf{y} - \boldsymbol{\Phi} \boldsymbol{\mu})] - \Re[\text{diag}(\mathbf{C}^T \boldsymbol{\Phi} \boldsymbol{\Sigma})]$. where $\mathbf{v}_y \in R^{G \times 1}$ Note:

Assuming that S represents the spacing distance between any two adjacent grid points along the Y-axis.

B.2 This subsection addresses the assumption of dependency for computing $\Delta \mathbf{x}$ and $\Delta \mathbf{y}$. It employs the same approach earlier stated but incorporates two variables: $(\Delta \mathbf{x}, \Delta \mathbf{y})$. From (3.4) and (3.5), the joint PDF of $(\Delta \mathbf{x}, \Delta \mathbf{y})$ is:

$$P(\mathbf{w}, \mathbf{y}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \Delta \mathbf{x}, \Delta \mathbf{y}) = P(\mathbf{y} | \mathbf{w}, \Delta \mathbf{x}, \Delta \mathbf{y}) P(\mathbf{w} | \boldsymbol{\alpha}) \quad (3.11)$$

$$P(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) P(\Delta \mathbf{x}) P(\Delta \mathbf{y})$$

It is important to note that it is preferable to maximize $E[\log P(\mathbf{y} | \mathbf{w}, \Delta \mathbf{x}, \Delta \mathbf{y})]$ rather than the (3.11) because in many probabilistic models, directly maximizing the joint distribution shows computational difficulties. A more convenient method for preserving the relationship between the observed data \mathbf{y} and the unknown variables $(\Delta \mathbf{x}, \Delta \mathbf{y})$ is to focus instead on maximizing the conditional distribution $E[\log P(\mathbf{y} | \mathbf{w}, \Delta \mathbf{x}, \Delta \mathbf{y})]$ given the variables that were observed \mathbf{w} .

The objective of maximizing $E[\log P(\mathbf{y} | \mathbf{w}, \Delta \mathbf{x}, \Delta \mathbf{y})]$, guided by the prior distributions $p(\Delta \mathbf{x})$ and $p(\Delta \mathbf{y})$, is to determine the optimal values of $(\Delta \mathbf{x}, \Delta \mathbf{y})$

that maximize the likelihood of the observed data \mathbf{y} .

$$E[\log P(\mathbf{y}|\mathbf{w}, \Delta\mathbf{x}, \Delta\mathbf{y})P(\Delta\mathbf{x})P(\Delta\mathbf{y})] = E\left\{\|\mathbf{y} - \Phi_{(\Delta\mathbf{x}, \Delta\mathbf{y})}\boldsymbol{\mu}\|^2\right\} \quad (3.12)$$

Let's denote $E\left\{\|\mathbf{y} - \Phi_{(\Delta\mathbf{x}, \Delta\mathbf{y})}\boldsymbol{\mu}\|^2\right\}$ as (Ω) , then we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega = & \Delta\mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{V}_x \Delta\mathbf{x} + \Delta\mathbf{y}^T \mathbf{V}_y \Delta\mathbf{y} + \Delta\mathbf{y} \mathbf{V}_{(x,y)} \Delta\mathbf{x} + M1 \\ & - 2\mathbf{p}_x \Delta\mathbf{x} - 2\mathbf{p}_y \Delta\mathbf{y} + 2\mathbf{s}_x \Delta\mathbf{x} + 2\mathbf{s}_y \Delta\mathbf{y} + M2 \\ & + \Delta\mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{K}_x \Delta\mathbf{x} + \Delta\mathbf{y}^T \mathbf{K}_y \Delta\mathbf{y} + 2\Delta\mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{K}_{x,y} \Delta\mathbf{y} \end{aligned} \quad (3.13)$$

The detailed derivation of (3.13) is provided in the Appendix (A). By taking the partial derivative with respect to $\Delta\mathbf{x}, \Delta\mathbf{y}$, respectively then setting to zero, we obtain:

$$\hat{\Delta\mathbf{x}} = [\mathbf{F}_x]^{-1}[\mathbf{j}_x - \boldsymbol{\rho}_x] \quad (3.14)$$

where

$$\mathbf{F}_x = \Re[\mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{B} \circ (\boldsymbol{\Sigma} + \boldsymbol{\mu}^T \boldsymbol{\mu})] \quad (3.15)$$

and

$$\mathbf{j}_x = \Re[\text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\mu}) \mathbf{B}^T (\mathbf{Y} - \Phi \boldsymbol{\mu})] - \Re[\text{diag}(\mathbf{B}^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma} \Phi)] \quad (3.16)$$

Note that those terms ($\mathbf{F}_x \in R^{G \times G}$, $\mathbf{j}_x \in R^{G \times 1}$) are similar to (2.34) and (2.35), respectively. However, $(\boldsymbol{\rho}_x) \in R^{G \times 1}$ is an additional term.

$$\boldsymbol{\rho}_x = [\mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{C} \circ (\boldsymbol{\mu}^t \boldsymbol{\mu} + \boldsymbol{\Sigma})]^T \Delta\mathbf{y} \quad (3.17)$$

Following the same procedure above to estimate $\Delta \mathbf{y}$ as follows,

$$\hat{\Delta \mathbf{y}} = [\mathbf{F}_y]^{-1}[\mathbf{j}_y - \boldsymbol{\rho}_y] \quad (3.18)$$

where

$$\mathbf{F}_y = \Re[\mathbf{C}^T \mathbf{C} \circ (\boldsymbol{\Sigma} + \boldsymbol{\mu}^T \boldsymbol{\mu})] \quad (3.19)$$

and

$$\mathbf{j}_y = \Re[\text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\mu}) \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{y} - \boldsymbol{\Phi} \boldsymbol{\mu}] - \Re[\text{diag}(\mathbf{C}^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma} \boldsymbol{\Phi})] \quad (3.20)$$

and

$$\boldsymbol{\rho}_y = [\mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{C} \circ (\boldsymbol{\mu}^t \boldsymbol{\mu} + \boldsymbol{\Sigma})] \Delta \mathbf{x} \quad (3.21)$$

and same details as showed after (3.16) with respect to $\Delta \mathbf{y}$. Where $\boldsymbol{\rho}_y \in R^{G \times 1}$, $\mathbf{F}_y \in R^{G \times G}$ and $\mathbf{j}_y \in R^{G \times 1}$

3.3 Energy Consumption Model in the WSNs

Reducing the consumption of energy is considered to be as one of the main challenges in the WSNs. Most of the sensor energy is used during the transmission procedure to CH. The quantization procedure is used first to transform the data into a digital format before sending it [33]. The energy consumed for data transmission is represented by (2.1) as [52, 61].

Depending on how each approach processes the data, different numbers of bits B may be needed to transmit the information to the CH. In[40], The Multilateration approach is applied to the detection of the targets. Where the sensors transmit the data bits for every target separately to the CH. Thus, the following formula determines the

number of bits needed to transmit data about all targets in the area of sensing to CH [33, 40].

$$B = y \log_2 \frac{D_{max}}{\Delta} \quad (3.22)$$

Where Δ is the acceptable quantization error, y is the number of targets, and D_{max} is the maximum predicted distance between targets and sensor nodes. Under the assumption of uniform quantization, and according to (3.22), the number of bits is directly proportional to the total number of targets detected within the sensing area, and the energy needed for sending the targets' information is:

$$E_{TX}^i = (\tau + v \times d_{i,CH}^\psi) \times y \log_2 \frac{D_{max}}{\Delta} \quad (3.23)$$

To minimise the volume of the data (number of bits) that are communicated by the sensors, the proposed approach and other approaches employing the CS like [33] have the sensors send all observed targets' relative distances in a single packet to the CH. Moreover, to achieve a similar quantization error as in the multilateration approach, the number of bits delivered to CH in the proposed approach is:

$$B = \log_2 \frac{y \times D_{max}}{\Delta} \quad (3.24)$$

Lastly, the energy needed for sending the data of targets is as follows.

$$E_{TX}^i = (\tau + v \times d_{i,CH}^\psi) \times \log_2 \frac{y \times D_{max}}{\Delta} \quad (3.25)$$

The amount of bits in the proposed approach is logarithmically proportionate to the total number of targets detected. Fewer bits are needed for the proposed multi-target detection approach than for the multilateration method.

3.4 Reducing Energy Consumption In the WSNs

This section proposes Adaptive Sparse Bayesian Learning (ASBL). Despite proposing a method that relies on employing fewer sensors to detect target locations, it improves energy efficiency even more. In comparison to the traditional Multilateration approach [40], a comparative analysis is performed to assess the accuracy and detection probability. Moreover, compared to using normal-SBL as in 2.5, the proposed strategy shows higher efficiency in decreasing energy consumption.

The target detection procedures carried out by the ASBL technique are not substantially different from those of the SBL. It sets itself differently with an extra step that involves estimating the diagonal elements (ξ) of the covariance matrix for the underlying (f), as specified in (3.26), (3.27) and (3.28). To reduce energy consumption by lowering the number of sensors employed in the target detection process. Initially, a small number of sensors is randomly chosen, and their readings are collected through the CH. Subsequently, the CH requests more sensor readings, each of which has a bigger impact on the detection results, until the system obtains enough amounts of readings to successfully detect the targets with the least amount of energy consumption using the lowest possible number of sensors. Accordingly, the decision on which sensor's readings to request is made by finding the maximum value in the ξ vector among the sensors that have not been requested. Therefore, it is necessary to estimate ξ .

Following the procedures outlined in Section (2.5), the first step involves computing and estimating the sparse weight vector w by determining its mean μ_w and covariance matrix Σ_w using equations (2.22) and (2.21). Afterwards, the values of the

hyper-parameters α and σ^2 are computed using equations (2.24) and (2.25). Finally, ξ is estimated by employing compressive sensing data. A Bayesian approach for estimating the underlying signal \mathbf{f} is applied to calculate ξ , as detailed in [86]. While some uncertainty in the weights \mathbf{w} is acknowledged, the signal $\mathbf{f} = \Phi\mathbf{w}$ remains the primary quantity of interest [86]. Since \mathbf{w} is derived from a multivariate Gaussian distribution [34] with mean and covariance as specified by (2.22) and (2.21), the posterior density function of \mathbf{f} is also a multivariate Gaussian distribution with mean and covariance [86].

$$E(\mathbf{f}) = \Phi\boldsymbol{\mu} \quad (3.26)$$

$$\text{Cov}(\mathbf{f}) = \Phi\Sigma\Phi^T \quad (3.27)$$

Where \mathbf{f} is $\in R^{N \times 1}$, $\text{Cov}(\mathbf{f})$ is $\in R^{N \times N}$ and $E(\mathbf{f})$ is $\in R^{N \times 1}$. The $\xi \in R^{N \times 1}$ is estimated concurrently with the underlying signal \mathbf{f} estimation, The diagonal elements of the covariance matrix in (3.27) perform as error bars [86] as follows:

$$\xi = \text{diag}(\text{Cov}(\mathbf{f})) \quad (3.28)$$

Analysis of the ξ indicates the sensor with the highest error. Then, the CH calls readings from this sensor, which has the highest error. This iterative process continues until a specific threshold is reached. In this case, the difference variance error within the Σ matrix between the previous summons and the current one becomes virtually little. As a result, gathering more sensor data is relevant to the detection process accuracy. This procedure is executed following Algorithm.1:

Algorithm 1: Proposed ASBL-Approach Algorithm

Input : Φ, \mathbf{y}

Output: w

Randomly choose initial n sensors' reading $\rightarrow \Phi(n, :), \mathbf{y}(n)$;
convergence \leftarrow false;

while \sim convergence **do**

 Calculate $\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \sigma^{-2}$ using Eqs. (2.22), (2.21), (2.24), and (2.25);

 Calculate $\boldsymbol{\xi}_i \leftarrow \boldsymbol{\xi}_i = \text{diag}(\text{Cov}(\mathbf{f}))$;

 Calculate $\max(\boldsymbol{\xi}_i)$;

$n_i \leftarrow \boldsymbol{\xi}_i(n_i) = \max(\boldsymbol{\xi}_i)$;

if $\sum_{g=1}^G |(\text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_i) - \text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{i-1}))| < \text{threshold}$ **then**

 convergence \leftarrow true;

else

 call n_i sensors' reading;

 Update $\mathbf{y} \leftarrow \mathbf{y}_{new} = \mathbf{y}(n; n_i)$;

 Update $\Phi \leftarrow \Phi_{new} = \Phi([n; n_i], :)$;

end

end

The algorithm functions as follows: It begins by randomly initializing the readings from n sensors and setting the convergence flag to false. In each iteration, essential values such as $\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}$, and σ^{-2} are calculated. Then, the vector $\boldsymbol{\xi}_i$ is updated, and its maximum value is used to refresh the sensor readings and data. The convergence of the algorithm is checked by comparing the difference between current and previous matrices $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_i$ and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{i-1}$ with a predefined threshold. If this difference is below the threshold, the algorithm is deemed converged and terminates. Otherwise, the process continues until convergence is achieved, ensuring precise detection based on sensor inputs where the term *threshold* refers to a value typically set very low. This value is

used to compare the error between the current and previous iterations. According to the algorithm above, if the error falls below this threshold, the algorithm is terminated. For simulation purposes, the threshold was set to 10^{-14} to ensure optimal detection performance.

Unlike using all the sensors in the sensing area, the proposed A-SBL algorithm requires the fewest amount of sensors to detect successfully. Avoiding the activation or calling of sensors' readings that with readings that don't contribute significantly to error reduction t improves energy conservation.

CHAPTER 4

SIMULATION AND RESULTS

4.1 Introduction

The simulation and results that are produced with MATLAB software are discussed in this chapter in two major sections. The section (4.2) describes the results of the suggested SBL approach to improve target detection. It compares it with both the traditional Multilateration [40] and BP [33] approaches that are described in (2.2) and (2.4). Moreover, the section (4.3) presents the results of applying the proposed A-SBL method, highlighting its advantages over the Multilateration approach, including reduced energy consumption and extended sensor lifespan.”

4.2 Simulation and Results for Targets Detection

Based on the targets’ situations, this section presents the results for two scenarios: One for the on-grid target and one for the off-grid target.

4.2.1 The on-grid Targets Detection

A sensing area with dimensions $100 \times 100 \text{ m}^2$ divided into 100 grid points is considered. The inter-spacing distance along the x-axis and y-axis directions between any two adjacent grid points is set to 10 m. A total of 50 sensors are deployed and randomly distributed in the sensing area to detect randomly the on-grid distributed

potential targets. 1000 Monte Carlo simulation trials are performed. In each trial, the sensors' and targets' locations vary randomly.

The performance of the proposed SBL approach is compared to the BP approach [33]. In addition, the multilateration approach [40] has been used as a benchmark. The multilateration approach demonstrates superior performance and relies on ToA for target detection. The performance of the three approaches is compared using the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve. Successful detection is claimed when accurately detecting and localizing all targets to their exact grid points. False detection is recorded when at least one false target is mistakenly detected.

Fig.4.1 shows the ROC curve for 15 targets. The Multilateration Approach demonstrates exceptionally high detection probability with zero false alarms. In comparison, the proposed SBL approach exhibits equivalent performance to the multilateration approach, maintaining both detection accuracy and false alarm rates. Conversely, the BP approach shows a slightly reduced detection probability and a lower rate of false alarms.

Figure 4.2 shows that when the target count increases to 20, both the multilateration method and the proposed SBL approach maintain similar performance to the 15-target scenario. In contrast, the BP method exhibits reduced efficiency, characterized by notably lower detection probabilities and an increased incidence of false alarms compared to the previously mentioned methods.

Figure 4.1: Detection of 15 targets.

Figure 4.2: Detection of 20 on-grid targets.

Fig.4.3 shows the performance comparison when the number of targets increases to 25. One can see that the proposed SBL approach as compared to the multilateration method still shows identical performance. Also, the BP approach shows a distinct decrease in detection performance, identified by a reduction in the probability of detection and a higher probability of false alarm. This is due to the increase in the number of targets, which affects the performance of the BP approach.

Figure 4.3: Detection of 25 on-grid targets.

In Fig.4.4, performance comparison among different approaches is demonstrated when the number of targets is set to 33. The proposed SBL approach exhibits a slight performance decrement compared to the multilateration approach, as indicated by a drop in detection probability. Nevertheless, the proposed approach can maintain a relatively low false alarm rate. In contrast, the BP approach shows significant degradation in terms of high false alarm rates and extremely low detection probability.

Figure 4.4: Detecting of 33 on-grid targets.

From the above simulation scenarios, the proposed SBL approach shows comparable performance to the multilateration approach for a relatively high number of targets. It is important to notice that the multilateration approach requires a lot of energy even though it is quite successful in detecting targets. On the other hand, the proposed SBL approach delivers similar results with a large decrease in energy consumption. Moreover, the proposed SBL approach is more efficient than the BP method; twice as many targets were successfully detected using the proposed method as using the BP method.

Table 4.1: Simulation Parameters For On-Grid Target Localization

Parameter Name	Description	Value
Sensing Area	Dimensions of the sensing area	$100 \times 100 \text{ m}^2$
Grid Points	Number of grid points	100
Inter-spacing Distance	Distance between adjacent grid points (x-axis and y-axis)	10 m
Number of Sensors	Total number of sensors deployed	50
Sensor Deployment	Distribution of sensors	Random
Target Distribution	Distribution of targets	Random
Monte Carlo Trials	Number of Monte Carlo simulation trials	1000
Performance Metric	Evaluation method	ROC Curve
Benchmark Approach	Comparison benchmark	Multilateration
Successful Detection Criteria	Detection accuracy	Exact grid point localization
False Detection Criteria	Error measurement	Detection of false targets

4.2.2 The off-grid Targets Detection

This subsection discusses the simulation and the outcomes when the targets are not on the predefined grid, where the targets have a specific displacement within the x or y coordinate, Two proposed approaches were compared for determining the displacements of each target relative to the nearest grid point. While the first approach calculated these displacements under the independence assumption, the second approach assumed dependence, where the x -axis displacement value is connected to or reliant upon the y -axis displacement as detailed in Section (3.2.2). The area of interest with dimensions $440 \times 440 \text{ m}^2$ is considered. The area is divided into 900 grid points, with an inter-spacing distance of 15 m. A total of 450 sensors are deployed randomly across the sensing area to detect off-grid targets. Monte Carlo simulations with 1000 trails are performed. In each trial, the sensors and targets are randomly distributed. Initially, each target is allocated a random grid point. Next, each target is randomly shifted from its assigned grid point along the x - and y -axes, with $\in (-\frac{S}{2}, \frac{S}{2})$.

Since the focus is on determining the off-grid target locations, a circle with a radius of $21.4m$ is assumed to surround each actual target, which is positioned at the center of this circle. Only when the estimated target is inside this circle can it be classified as a detected target. Moreover, the circle's radius is set to $19m$ and $15m$ for a scenario with 8 targets. This assumption is necessary as off-grid displacements in the targets could lead to errors, and the estimate gives the actual target location with deviations. Finally, the distances among targets are constrained to be at least $30m$ to avoid multiple targets from being allocated to the same detection region.

Fig.4.5 shows the ROC curve for 5 off-grid targets. The proposed approaches manifest notably extremely high detection and low false alarm rates. It is also obvious that there is no distinction in terms of performance between both methods: the dependent approach and the independent approach.

Figure 4.5: Detection of 5 off-grid targets.

As Fig.4.6, when the off-grid targets' number is raised to 10, the ROC curve shows that both approaches' performance slightly dropped with a very tiny rise in false alarm rates and a small decrease in detection probability. Furthermore, there was a similar pattern in both approaches' performance.

Figure 4.6: Detection of 10 off-grid targets.

As the number of off-grid targets increased to 13 as in Fig.4.7, the ROC curve shows performance reduction for both approaches, with a slight improvement in the case of dependent displacements. With identical detection probability ratios and a small spike in false alarms for both approaches, this difference is almost insignificant and can be ignored.

Figure 4.7: Detection of 13 off-grid targets.

The ROC curve in Fig.4.8 shows a drop in performance when the number of off-grid targets is raised to 15, as compared to the prior scenario. A rise in the false alarm rate is shown by the performance curve's appearance, which is a sharp straight line. Furthermore, there was no discernible variance between the detection probability ratios for both approaches decreased compared to the case with 13 targets previously.

Fig.4.9 shows the ROC curve for 20 off-grid targets, Compared to previous scenarios, we can observe a decline in performance, as represented by more false alarm rates and reduced detection probability ratios.

Figure 4.8: Detection of 15 off-grid targets.

Figure 4.9: Detection of 20 off-grid targets.

Fig.4.10 shows the ROC curve for the scenario with 8 off-grid targets and 15m detection radius. The performance is modest with somewhat unfavorable detection probability ratios and false alarm rates.

Figure 4.10: Detection of circle 15m.

In Fig.4.11, The ROC curve indicates an improvement in performance efficiency for 8 off-grid targets at a higher radius value of 19m. The enhancement of the probability of detection ratios and the decrease in false alarm rates are indications of this improvement. When the circle's radius is increased from 15m to 19m, the circle around the actual target expands. As a consequence, the estimated target has a higher chance of falling inside this circle. This explains the reason for the improvement in the performance curve.

Figure 4.11: Detection of circle 19m.

From the previous figures, it is evident that the two proposed methods for detecting off-grid targets performed comparably, with the dependency approach demonstrating a slight performance improvement. Although this advantage is marginal, it appears that, in some cases, the dependency approach is less error-prone and more accurate in locating off-grid targets. The distinction between the two methods may not be immediately apparent due to the curves in the figures representing averages over 1,000 trials.

It is important to note that the dependent approach does not use the equations (3.7) and (3.9), which are used in the independent approach to correct estimated displacement values if any values in both Δx , Δy are found outside of the boundary range that has been set as in (3.8) and (3.10). This implies that the proposed dependent off-grid approach has more sophisticated theoretical accuracies compared to the independent assumption approach.

Nevertheless, The proposed approach achieved up to 15 off-grid targets with a significant probability of detection and a low percentage of false alarms, resulting in relatively high detection rates. Thus, off-grid target detection using the proposed approach was successful. It is apparent that, in comparison to on-grid targets, off-grid targets require more complex computations. Off-grid errors lead to estimates of target locations that are not accurate.

Table 4.2: Simulation Parameters For Off-Grid Target Localization

Parameter	Value
Sensing Area Dimensions	$440 \times 440 \text{ m}^2$
Number of Grid Points	900
Grid-Point Spacing	15 m
Number of Sensors	450
Number of Targets	5 : 20
Circle Radius for Target Detection (Initial)	21.4 m
Circle Radius for Target Detection (Alternate)	$19 \text{ m}, 15 \text{ m}$
Minimum Distance Between Targets	30 m
Monte Carlo Simulations	1000 trials
Target Shift Range	$(-7.5, 7.5)$

4.3 Simulation and Results for Energy Reduction in WSNs

This section compares the proposed A-SBL approach with the proposed SBL method and the multilateration approach, which is used as a comparison benchmark, where the ToA measurements are used for target detection [40].

Two metrics are used to evaluate this comparison. First, the ROC curve is used to compare the respective performances of the detection for all the approaches. Second, the amounts of the energy consumption of the proposed A-SBL approach and the SBL method were shown relative to the amounts of the energy consumption of the multilateration method. In addition, the energy ratios were calculated concerning how they represent the average energy consumed by each sensor per single target.

Where the energy consumption by A-SBL and SBL relative to multilateration is given by:

$$\text{Energy Consumption Ratio}_{\text{A-SBL}} = \left(\frac{\text{Energy Consumption}_{\text{A-SBL}}}{\text{Energy Consumption}_{\text{MULTI}}} \right) \times 100\% \quad (4.1)$$

$$\text{Energy Consumption Ratio}_{\text{SBL}} = \left(\frac{\text{Energy Consumption}_{\text{SBL}}}{\text{Energy Consumption}_{\text{MULTI}}} \right) \times 100\% \quad (4.2)$$

Consider a $100 \times 100 \text{ m}^2$ sensing area sampled into 100 grid points. 10 metres is the inter-spacing distance between any two adjacent grid points along the x and y axes. A total of 50 sensors were randomly distributed within the sensing region to detect randomly distributed possible on-grid targets. 1000 Monte Carlo simulation experiments were conducted. The placements of the targets and sensors change at random in each trial.

Fig.4.12(a), shows the ROC curve for 5 targets. The performance of all compared approaches shows an especially high probability of detection and no false alarms. Fig.4.12(b) presents the amount of energy consumed in the SBL method and the proposed A-SBL approach relative to the energy consumed in the Multilateration approach. The proposed A-SBL approach consumed less energy than the SBL method, whereas, in the A-SBL method, the average energy consumed per sensor for a single target is 53% of the energy consumed in the Multilateration approach. Similarly, the SBL method consumes 82% of the energy used in the multilateration strategy.

Figure 4.12: Comparing the energy consumption and detection performance for 5 targets of the A-SBL (using 5 initial sensors), multilateration, and normal SBL approaches.

Fig.4.13(a) shows the ROC curves when the number of targets is increased to 15. The performance of both the proposed A-SBL and SBL approaches shows an especially high probability of detection and a low rate of false alarms. As in Fig.4.13(b), the A-SBL method consumed 30% of the energy consumed by the Multilateration approach, while 31% was consumed by the SBL method. This indicates that the proposed approach consumes the lowest amount of energy relative to the other two approaches.

Figure 4.13: Comparing the energy consumption and detection performance for 15 targets of the A-SBL (using 5 initial sensors), multilateration, and normal SBL approaches.

In Fig4.14(a), when the number of targets is increased to 30, a reduction in the detection probability is noticed, which indicates a minor performance degradation for both the proposed A-SBL and SBL approaches relative to the Multilateration method. However, the proposed methods can continue to have a low false alarm rate. Additionally, Fig4.14(b) shows that both the proposed SBL and A-SBL approaches consumed the same amount of energy, equivalent to 17% of the energy consumed in the Multilateration approach.

Figure 4.14: Comparing the energy consumption and detection performance for 30 Targets of the A-SBL (using 5 initial sensors), multilateration, and normal SBL approaches.

When the number of initial sensors rises to 15, the Figures.4.15(a) and 4.15(b) show ROC curves for 5 and 15 targets, respectively. Where both the proposed A-SBL and SBL approaches show identical performance with the multilateration Approach by high detection probabilities and low false alarm rates for both 5 and 15 targets.

Figure 4.15: Comparing the Detection Performance of the A-SBL (using 15 initial sensors), multilateration, and normal SBL approaches.

In contrast to the multilateration approach, a decline in performance is seen in Fig.4.16 for both the A-SBL and the SBL approach while the number of targets is increased to 30.

Figure 4.16: Comparing the detection performance of the A-SBL for 30 targets (using 15 initial sensors), multilateration, and normal SBL approaches.

Regarding energy consumption, Fig.4.17(a) illustrates that for a set of 5 targets, the energy consumed by the suggested A-SBL approach was 45% of the energy consumed by the Multilateration method. In contrast, the SBL method had an 82% energy consumption rate. When the number of targets increased to 15 as in Fig.4.17(b), the energy consumed by the A-SBL approach was 28% of the energy consumed by the Multilateration method while with the SBL method is 30%.

Figure 4.17: Comparing the energy consumption of the A-SBL (using 15 initial sensors), multilateration, and normal SBL approaches.

Finally, as in Fig.4.18 the energy consumed by the SBL method and the A-SBL approach was the same when the number of targets reached 30, accounting for 17% of the energy consumed by the Multilateration method.

Figure 4.18: Comparing the energy consumption for 30 targets of the A-SBL (using 15 initial sensors), multilateration, and normal SBL approaches.

As the number of targets increases, the energy consumption of the proposed A-SBL approach increases correspondingly and eventually reaches a level similar to that of the proposed SBL method. As such, a higher number of targets requires an increased number of sensors. This means that for the proposed method's procedure to successfully detect targets, it needs to take into account the readings from other sensors. Thus, to guarantee successful detection when the number of targets reaches 30 as shown in Figs.4.14(b) and 4.18, the proposed A-SBL approach needs to collect readings from every sensor that is visible inside the sensing area. Consequently, the energy consumed is the same as when using the SBL method.

The energy consumed by the proposed A-SBL approach decreases when the number of initial sensors increases, compared to the Multilateration and SBL methods. When there were 5 targets the energy consumption reduced from 53% to 43% as the number of initial sensors raised from 5 to 15 as shown in Figures.4.12(b),4.17(a). Similarly, when there were 15 targets the energy consumption dropped from 30% to 28% as shown in Figs.4.13(b) and 4.17(b). Because there aren't enough sensors to detect targets in real locations, the process of choosing the next sensor is quasi-random due to the small number of initial sensors. As a result, it may be considered that the chosen sensor is perfect for detecting false targets. This means that adding a random sensor into the chosen sensors' group would probably not engage with real targets until a sufficient amount of sensors is acquired. Thus, actual targets are detected and the process is terminated since the next sensor will be most effective at detecting these actual targets. However, as the number of initial sensors increases, the probability of detecting real targets also increases. As such, the optimal sensor for these real targets is chosen as the next one. Therefore, by preventing choosing random sensors that are inactive for detecting targets, the number of used and energy consumption is decreased.

Table 4.3: Summary of Results for Performance and Energy Consumption of A-SBL and SBL methods Compared and Relative to the multilateration approach as Eqs. (4.1),(4.2) respectively

Initial Sensors	Targets	Detection Prob.	False Alarms	(A-SBL)	(SBL)
5	5	High	None	53%	82%
	15	High	None	30%	31%
	30	Reduced	Low	17%	17%
15	5	High	None	43%	82%
	15	High	None	28%	30%
	30	Reduced	Low	17%	17%

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

5.1 Conclusion

Under the analysis that is conducted on the target detection in both the off-grid and on-grid scenarios, in addition to the energy consumption, the following conclusions have been reached:

1. The proposed SBL method for target detection in both on-grid and off-grid scenarios has shown superior detection capabilities compared to previous CS-based approaches. Also, it effectively estimates off-grid target locations, with the dependent approach providing theoretically more accurate results than the independent approach. However, performance may decline if the number of targets exceeds a certain threshold, potentially violating the sparsity condition. To maintain high detection rates and adherence to sparsity requirements, it is advisable to use the SBL method in areas with a high sensor density.
2. The proposed A-SBL method for target detection in WSNs has shown substantial improvements in energy efficiency compared to both the SBL and Multilateration approaches. Using ROC curves to assess performance, the A-SBL method is

effective in reducing energy consumption by selectively activating only the necessary sensors, which enhances detection probability while minimizing energy use. This method achieves high detection rates with fewer sensors, especially in scenarios with fewer targets, leading to prolonged sensors' lifetime. However, the A-SBL approach may perform similarly to SBL when the number of targets exceeds a certain threshold, as it may need to use all available sensors for accurate detection, and its effectiveness decreases with increasing targets due to limitations in sparsity conditions.

5.2 Future Work

This section involves some suggested ideas for future research about extending the lifetime of the WSNs' sensors and both Multi-target and Off-grid target detections:

1. Employing the A-SBL approach to detect the off-grid targets to minimize energy consumption.
2. Using artificial intelligence (AI) to detect the off-grid target locations. Machine learning, Neural networks and other AI methods may greatly improve the detection of target locations in WSNs.
3. Combining the SBL and the A-SBL approaches for target tracking to enhance tracking accuracy and reduce energy consumption

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CHAPTER A

APPENDIX: DERIVATION OF EQUATION 3.13

$$\begin{aligned}
 E \left\{ \|\mathbf{y} - \Phi_{(\Delta\mathbf{x}, \Delta\mathbf{y})} \boldsymbol{\mu}\|_2^2 \right\} &= \overbrace{\|\mathbf{y} - (\Phi + \mathbf{B}\Delta\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{C}\Delta\mathbf{y})\|_2^2}^{\text{PART1}} \\
 &\quad + \underbrace{\text{tr}([\Phi + \mathbf{B}\Delta\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{C}\Delta\mathbf{y}]^T \Sigma [\Phi + \mathbf{B}\Delta\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{C}\Delta\mathbf{y}])}_{\text{PART2}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{A.1}$$

where $\text{diag}(\Delta\mathbf{x}) = \Delta\mathbf{x}$.

and $\text{diag}(\Delta\mathbf{y}) = \Delta\mathbf{y}$.

For part one:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\|\mathbf{y} - (\Phi + \mathbf{B}\Delta\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{C}\Delta\mathbf{y})\|_2^2 \\
 &= \|(\mathbf{y} - \Phi\boldsymbol{\mu}) - (\mathbf{B}\text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\mu})\Delta\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{B}\text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\mu})\Delta\mathbf{x})\|_2^2
 \end{aligned}$$

Then it's easy to simplify the above to get:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{PART1} &= M1 - 2[\text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\mu})\mathbf{B}^T(\mathbf{y} - \Phi\boldsymbol{\mu})]^T \Delta\mathbf{x} \\
 &\quad - 2[\text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\mu})\mathbf{C}^T(\mathbf{B} - \Phi\boldsymbol{\mu})]^T \Delta\mathbf{y} + \Delta\mathbf{x}^T [\mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{B} \circ \boldsymbol{\mu}\boldsymbol{\mu}^T] \Delta\mathbf{x}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$+ \Delta \mathbf{y}^T [\mathbf{C}^T \mathbf{C} \circ \boldsymbol{\mu} \boldsymbol{\mu}^T] \Delta \mathbf{y} + \Delta \mathbf{y}^T [\mathbf{C}^T \mathbf{B} \circ \boldsymbol{\mu} \boldsymbol{\mu}^T] \Delta \mathbf{x}.$$

Now part two is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & Tr([\Phi + \mathbf{B} \Delta \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{C} \Delta \mathbf{y}]^T \Sigma [\Phi + \mathbf{B} \Delta \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{C} \Delta \mathbf{y}]) \\ &= Tr[\Phi \Sigma \Phi + \Phi \Sigma \mathbf{B}^T [\text{diag}(\Delta \mathbf{x})]^T + \Phi \Sigma \mathbf{C}^T [\text{diag}(\Delta \mathbf{y})]^T \\ &+ \mathbf{B}^T \Sigma \mathbf{B} [\text{diag}(\Delta \mathbf{x})]^T \text{diag}(\Delta \mathbf{x}) \\ &+ \mathbf{B}^T \Sigma \mathbf{C} [\text{diag}(\Delta \mathbf{x})]^T \text{diag}(\Delta \mathbf{y}) \\ &+ \mathbf{C}^T \Sigma \mathbf{B} [\text{diag}(\Delta \mathbf{y})]^T \text{diag}(\Delta \mathbf{x}) \\ &+ \mathbf{C}^T \Sigma \mathbf{C} [\text{diag}(\Delta \mathbf{y})]^T \text{diag}(\Delta \mathbf{y}) \\ &+ \mathbf{B}^T \Sigma \Phi \text{diag}(\Delta \mathbf{x}) + \mathbf{C}^T \Sigma \Phi \text{diag}(\Delta \mathbf{y})]. \end{aligned}$$

Also, after easy simplification, part two became:

$$\begin{aligned} PART2 &= M2 + 2[\text{diag}(\mathbf{B}^T \Phi \Sigma)]^T \Delta \mathbf{x} \\ &+ 2[\text{diag}(\mathbf{C}^T \Phi \Sigma)]^T \Delta \mathbf{y} + \Delta \mathbf{x}^T [\mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{B} \circ \Sigma] \Delta \mathbf{x} \end{aligned}$$

$$+ \Delta \mathbf{y}^T [\mathbf{C}^T \mathbf{C} \circ \Sigma] \Delta \mathbf{y} + 2 \Delta \mathbf{x}^T [\mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{C} \circ \Sigma] \Delta \mathbf{y}$$

So, When summing Part1 and Part2 equation 3.13 got and must Taking into consideration the following symbols:

$$\text{NOTE: } \mathbf{V}_x = (\mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{B} \circ \boldsymbol{\mu}^T \boldsymbol{\mu}), \text{ and } \mathbf{V}_y = (\mathbf{C}^T \mathbf{C} \circ \boldsymbol{\mu}^T \boldsymbol{\mu}).$$

$$\text{and } \mathbf{p}_x = [\text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\mu}) \cdot \mathbf{B}^T (\mathbf{y} - \Phi \boldsymbol{\mu})]^T.$$

$$\text{and } \mathbf{p}_y = [\text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\mu}) \cdot \mathbf{C}^T (\mathbf{Y} - \Phi \boldsymbol{\mu})]^T.$$

$$\text{and } \mathbf{s}_x = [\text{diag}(\mathbf{B}^T \Sigma \Phi)]^T, \text{ and } \mathbf{s}_y = [\text{diag}(\mathbf{C}^T \Sigma \Phi)]^T.$$

$$\text{and } \mathbf{K}_x = (\Sigma \circ \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{B}), \text{ and } \mathbf{K}_y = (\Sigma \circ \mathbf{C}^T \mathbf{C}).$$

$$\text{and } \mathbf{V}_{x,y} = (\mathbf{C}^T \mathbf{B} \circ \boldsymbol{\mu}^T \boldsymbol{\mu}), \text{ and } \mathbf{K}_{x,y} = (\Sigma \circ \mathbf{C}^T \mathbf{B}).$$

and all of $(M1, M2)$ is constant term Independent with both $(\Delta \mathbf{x}, \Delta \mathbf{y})$.

LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

1. . Mustafa Abdul. AL-Zurfi, Ahmed Al Hilli, Mohanad Al-Ibadi. Enhancing Energy Efficiency in Wireless Sensor Networks via Adaptive Sparse Bayesian Learning. In *Proceedings of the 15th International IEEE Conference on Computing, Communication and Networking Technologies (ICCCNT)*. (Accepted for Publication)
2. . Mustafa Abdul. AL-Zurfi, Ahmed Al Hilli, Mohanad Al-Ibadi. Enhancing Off-Grid Target Detection in Wireless Sensor Networks via Sparse Bayesian Learning. In *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Engineering and Science to Achieve the Sustainable Development Goals*. (Accepted for Publication)

الخلاصة

تُعدُّ استنزاف الطاقة تحديًا كبيرًا في شبكات الاستشعار اللاسلكية (*WSNs*). بينما يُعَدُّ ضغط الاستشعار (*CS*) وسيلة فعّالة لتقليل استهلاك الطاقة، ولكنه يواجه بعض القيود، مثل القدرة المحدودة على كشف عدد معين من الأهداف وافترض أن الأهداف تقع على المواقع الشبكية (*On-Grid Targets*) المعدة مسبقًا. اقترحت هذه الرسالة استخدام التعلم البايزي المتناثر (*SBL*) لكشف الأهداف في شبكات الاستشعار اللاسلكية. تعمل طريقة (*SBL*) على تعزيز دقة كشف الهدف وتحقيق ضعف كشف الهدف تقريبًا مقارنة بالطرق الأخرى مثل *BasisPursuit* (*BP*) حيث نجحت طريقة (*SBL*) في كشف ما يصل إلى 30 هدفًا بأداء كشف عالٍ للغاية وبالمقارنة مع طريقة (*BP*) التي حققت كشف ناجح لـ 15 هدفًا فقط في ظل نفس الظروف البيئية. كما ويوفر الـ (*SBL*) نموذجًا لكشف الأهداف التي تكون خارج الإحداثيات أو المواقع الشبكية (*Off-Grid Targets*).

تأخذ سيناريوهات تموضع الأهداف خارج الإحداثيات الشبكية في الاعتبار متغيرين: الإزاحة على المحور السيني والمحور الصادي. حيث أسفرت نتائج كشف الأهداف التي تكون خارج الإحداثيات الشبكية أن النهج المقترح الذي يفترض الترابط (*Dependent*) بين الإزاحتين، يمكنه تحديد مواقع الأهداف بفعالية ضمن إطار الفرضيات النظرية. وهذا يتناقض مع نهج فرض عدم الترابط (*Independent*) والذي قد لا يحقق نفس مستوى الدقة في بعض الأحيان.

علاوة على ذلك، اقترحت هذه الرسالة نهجًا تكييفيًا للتعلم البايزي المتناثر (*A-SBL*) لزيادة عمر بطاريات المستشعرات في شبكات الاستشعار اللاسلكية. من خلال دمج النموذج البايزي مع الاستشعار المضغوط التكييفي (*A-CS*)، تقلل المنهجية من عدد المستشعرات المطلوبة لكشف الأهداف بنجاح. في البداية، يتم اختيار عدد قليل من المستشعرات عشوائيًا، ثم بعد ذلك يتم استدعاء المستشعرات التي توفر أكبر قدر من المعلومات، محققًا أكبر تقليل للخطأ. يعزز هذا النهج استخدام الموارد وكفاءة الطاقة، مما يحسن الأداء العام للشبكة. تؤكد النتائج أن هذه الطريقة تقلل بشكل كبير من استهلاك الطاقة مقارنة بالأساليب الأخرى، خاصة مع عدد الأهداف القليلة. مما

يسهم في تقدم تكنولوجيا شبكات الاستشعار اللاسلكية. حيث أظهرت النتائج أن استهلاك الطاقة بطريقة (A – SBL) كان 53% نسبة الى الطاقة المستهلكة بالطريقة التقليدية في حالة 5 أهداف. ومع زيادة عدد الأهداف إلى 15 و 30 ، انخفض استهلاك الطاقة إلى 30% و 17% على التوالي، من الطاقة المستهلكة بالطريقة التقليدية. بالإضافة إلى ذلك، عندما تمت زيادة أجهزة الاستشعار الأولية إلى 15 بدلاً من 5 ، كان استهلاك الطاقة للطريقة المقترحة 48% و 28% و 17% لـ 5 و 15 و 30 هدفاً على التوالي.

الكشف عن الأهداف خارج الإحداثيات الشبكية في شبكات
الاستشعار اللاسلكية باستخدام التعلم البايزي المتناثر

الرسالة

مقدمة الى قسم هندسة تقنيات الاتصالات كجزء من متطلبات نيل درجه الماجستير في
هندسة الاتصالات

تقدمَ بها

مصطفى عبدالرحمن جبار الزرفي

أشرف

الأستاذ المساعد الدكتور

أحمد محمد زكي

المدرس الدكتور

مهند أحمد العبادي

2024

جمهورية العراق
وزارة التعليم العالي والبحث العلمي
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الكلية التقنية الهندسية نجف

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